

HUBS MANUAL FOR THE M9-10 CONSULTATION WORKSHOP

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Table of Contents

A. Workshop Overview	7
A.1. Goals and outcomes	7
A.2. Programme	8
A.3. General guidelines	8
A.4 The Hubs Manual for the M9-M10 Consultation Workshop.....	10
A.5 Assistance and support	11
B. Recruitment.....	14
B.1 Recruitment criteria	14
B.2 Rationale for participating	15
B.2.1 General considerations.....	16
B.2.2 Civil Society Organizations (CSOs)	18
B.2.3 Education community	19
B.2.4 Industry and business representatives	21
B.2.5 Policymakers.....	22
B.2.6 Researchers and innovators.....	23
B.3 Invitations	25
B.4 Information package and previous work from participants	25
C. Dissemination plan	28
C.1 Before the workshop	28
C.2 During the workshop	29
C.3 After the workshop.....	29
D. Staff competences, skills, and duties	31
D.1 Building on group interaction.....	31
D.2 Moderator competencies.....	32
D.3 Moderator skills	33
D.3.1 Listening	33
D.3.2 Positive accepting	34
D.3.3 Process interventions.....	35
D.3.4 Dealing with resistance	36
D.4 Further readings	38

E. Session guidelines	40
E.1 Session 1: Introduction to Workshop and RRI Tools	40
E.1.1 Session 1 overview: goals, format, duration, results	40
E.1.2 Session 1 guidelines	40
WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION	41
E.2 Session 2: RRI Working Definition	43
E.2.1 Session 2 overview: goals, format, duration, results	43
E.2.2 Session 2 guidelines	43
EXERCISE 0. ON-GOING ACTIVITY.....	43
EXERCISE 1. THE RRI WORKING DEFINITION	44
EXERCISE 2. EXPERIENCES OF PARTICIPANTS	44
E.3 Session 3: Compilation of Promising RRI Practices	46
E.3.1 Session 3 overview: goals, format, duration, results	46
E.3.2 Session 3 guidelines	46
EXERCISE 3. STRONG AND WEAK POINTS OF PROMISING PRACTICES	46
EXERCISE 4. WHAT CHARACTERIZES PROMISING PRACTICES?	47
E.4 Session 4: Stakeholder Consultation	49
E.4.1 Session 4 overview: goals, format, duration, results	49
E.4.2 Session 4 guidelines	49
EXERCISE 5. INTRODUCTION TO SESSION 4	50
EXERCISE 6. OBSTACLES AND OPPORTUNITIES.....	50
EXERCISE 7. IDENTIFY ACTIONS AND SOLUTIONS.....	52
EXERCISE 8. COMPILATION OF NEEDS FOR STAKEHOLDER ACTIONS AND SOLUTIONS.....	53
EXERCISE 9. CLOSURE, FEEDBACK, AND INTERPERSONAL EXCHANGE	54
F. Evaluation	57
G. Reporting	59
Annex I. Stakeholder mapping tables	62
Annex II. Invitation letter template	73
Annex III. Information package	75
1. RRI Information Sheet	75
2. Examples of promising RRI practices	77
3. Promising RRI practice question sheet	79
4. Informed consent	81

Annex IV. Session scripts with guidelines.....	84
Session 1: Welcome and introduction	84
Session 2: RRI working definition	87
Session 3: Compilation of promising RRI practices	93
Session 4: Stakeholder consultation	96
Summary table	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Annex V. Evaluation questionnaire	114
Annex VI. Follow up e-mail survey template.....	117
Annex VII. Reporting template.....	121
Annex VIII. Checklist for organising the workshop	131

WORKSHOP OVERVIEW

A. Workshop Overview

A.1. Goals and outcomes

During September and October of the first year of RRI Tools (months 9 and 10 of the project -M9-M10-) the National Hub Coordinators (NHCs) are responsible for the organisation of two workshops, as detailed in the Document of Work (DoW).

These two workshops, labelled as a whole as **M9-M10 Consultation Workshop**, are based on the working definition of RRI (WP1) and the stakeholders mapping (WP2) to guarantee that the voice of a wide range of RRI stakeholder profiles across the 19 hub regions is heard and ensure that the Toolkit reflects the concerns, needs, and constraints of its future users.

The aim of this M9-M10 Consultation Workshop is to discuss with participants the RRI working definition and their practical experiences with RRI, collect and evaluate promising practices, and assess the stakeholders' needs and constraints when putting RRI into practice.

The **main goals** of the M9-M10 Consultation Workshop are thus:

- gather feedback on the project's working definition of RRI;
- collect, examine, and make a first classification of promising RRI practices;
- identify the needs and constraints of all stakeholders involved in the RRI process;
- receive ideas of potential tools for the RRI Toolkit;
- gain an overview of the differences across stakeholder groups and EU countries;
- start building a Community of Practice (CoP) across Europe.

From the whole workshop run by each NHC we expect the following **outcomes**:

- a list of comments to the preliminary RRI working definition;
- a compilation of all promising RRI practices collected by NHCs and workshop participants with a preselection of the 10 most promising practices;
- a list of opportunities and obstacles related to RRI per stakeholder group;
- a list of suggested solutions to address the needs per stakeholder group;
- a list of potential tools to address the most relevant needs per stakeholder group;
- an engaged, mobilized group of persons that will join the Community of Practice.

Besides these outcomes, directly related to WP1 (Definition and Good Practices), WP2 (Stakeholder Assessment), and WP3 (Toolkit Production and CoP), the workshops across all the Hubs will also contribute to the other aspects of the project:

- Training and Advocacy (WP4), by setting the basis for the future activities to be carried out by the NHCs in the third year of the project;
- Evaluation (WP5); both of the project and of project's activities
- Dissemination (WP6), by actively disseminating the project on the occasion of the workshop and by promoting the digital platform and social media.

Proper execution of the workshop, as well as collection and report of its results in a standard format to be analysed and implemented into other WPs, is crucial for the success of RRI Tools. To accomplish these goals each NHC will have the support of its Hub members – who will receive financial and technical support – and the European hubs’ coordinator (Ciência Viva), as well as the support of concerned WP leaders, project coordination and the rest of the Consortium.

A.2. Programme

The whole workshop has been designed to take place in a single day (6 hours and a half plus breaks and lunch time), organized as detailed below. However, the methodology allows certain flexibility for minor adaptations to address the logistical and cultural particularities of each hub, so NHCs can adapt this structure to their needs. In this sense, if needed, the workshop can easily be split in two separate half-day events (given that the budget for the NHC allows this rearrangement). Any adaptation, however, should be discussed beforehand with the Hubs coordination (Ciência Viva).

In any case, NHCs are strongly encouraged to keep the same participants for the whole workshop, since the contents of the second part (Session 4) highly depend on those of the first part (Sessions 1 to 3).

Considering a single-day structure, the whole workshop is structured as follows:

Morning	Session 1	Introduction to Workshop and RRI Tools	35'
	Session 2	RRI Working Definition	1h 35' + break times
	Session 3	Compilation of Promising RRI Practices	1h 20' + break times
Lunch			45' - 1h
Afternoon	Session 4	Stakeholder Consultation	3h + break times
TOTAL			6h 30' + breaks & lunch

A.3. General guidelines

The preparation of the workshop requires a significant effort in time and human resources from the NHCs, so they should start well in advance. This section provides an overview of the workshop requirements, but NHCs need to read carefully the whole Manual (see A.4), where they will find detailed guidelines on how to select an adequate group of participants that covers a wide spectrum of stakeholders, organizations and RRI aspects, and how to organize, announce, host, conduct, and report appropriately the event.

Calendar

- **M7.** Recruitment and invitations must start well in advance, preferably in July.
- **M8.** Dissemination requires planning: inform EuroScience (WP6) of the date of the event at least 6 weeks in advance.
- **M8-M9.** Prepare the promotional material of RRI Tools and of your institution in advance and disseminate the event through different channels.
- **M8-M9.** Translate to your own language any material deemed necessary (information package, questionnaires, presentations, etc.).

- **M9-M10.** The workshop must be carried out between September and October.
- **M10.** Work does not finish with the workshop: evaluation (including a follow up e-mail), dissemination and reporting (a single report in English) information has to be delivered by the end of October to be analysed before 2014 ends (M12).
- **M11+.** Follow up the contacts you made to strengthen the CoP around your Hub

Participants

- NHCs will identify and mobilize representatives of each stakeholder group (civil society organisations, education, industry, policy making and research).
- The group of attendees should be 15 people (\pm 1-2), 3 per stakeholder group.
- Postpone the workshop with less than 2 participants per stakeholder group.

Recruitment

- Invitation letters must be reinforced by personal and direct contact (follow-up calls, face-to-face if possible) to increase the response rate.
- Invite more participants than the 15 needed to account for possible dropouts.
- Clearly explain why the participation in the workshop will be of interest for the stakeholder.
- The informed consent form should be translated and, if needed, adapted to local contexts.
- Provide the selected attendees with an information package about RRI, a summary of the project, basic dissemination material, the practicalities of the event and the informed consent form.
- The document "[Useful links and documents related to RRI](#)", in the Hubs' Basecamp section, offers references that may help to prepare the event.

Staff

- Determine the persons who will act as moderator and assistant and provide them with adequate training beforehand.
- NHCs should provide stakeholders with background information about RRI before discussing needs and constraints. For this, hubs can take into account possible contributions from external invited experts or other stakeholders during Session 2.

Venue

- Choose a quiet location, big enough for 20 people to move comfortably.
- Better if it offers the possibility to also work separated in five small groups.
- It should be equipped with projector, screen, flip chart and pin wall.

The workshop

- The event requires significant logistics and a good practical organization.
- Be on time! You will need time to arrange the room (materials, table arrangement, refreshments, etc.) before the participants can come in.
- All the necessary material (stationery, sheets, forms, lists, agendas, etc.) has to be organized and their functionality checked well in advance.
- During the event a considerable amount of information has to be collected (observations, filled in sheets, pictures, flip charts, evaluation questionnaires...).

A.4 The Hubs Manual for the M9-M10 Consultation Workshop

For the purpose of assisting NHCs throughout the M9-M10 Consultation Workshop, a set of tools have been designed and assembled in a toolkit (this Hubs Manual), from the recruitment of attendees to the final reporting. These tools are organized in the following sections:

Recruitment

Section B includes a set of guidelines to help NHCs identify and mobilize representatives of each stakeholder group within their hub area. It contains specifications for the overall composition of the groups, recruitment criteria, mapping tables of each stakeholder group (Annex I), a rationale for inviting potential candidates to the workshop and for potential issues regarding each stakeholder group, an invitation letter template (Annex II), and an information package (Annex III).

Dissemination plan

Section C provides a dissemination plan with relevant information regarding the communication strategy carried out by each hub before, during and after the workshop. It includes the use of different channels and materials.

Staff competences, skills, and duties

Section D explains the skills and duties of the NHCs staff that will act as moderators and assistants during the workshop, including how to build a positive group interaction and deal with different issues common to participatory events.

Session guidelines

Section E provides all the information regarding organisational aspects of each session of the workshop: detailed directions on how to conduct them (including the procedures, methodological guidelines, goals, timeframe, materials and outcomes), supporting PowerPoint presentations, and scripts to be used during the workshop (Annex IV). To facilitate all these tasks a checklist for organising the workshop (Annex VIII) summarizes all the activities that have to be done before, during, and after the workshop, plus everything that needs to be gathered, prepared and brought to the sessions.

Evaluation

Section F describes how the workshops will be evaluated and is complemented with an evaluation questionnaire (Annex V) to be distributed and filled by attendees at the end of the workshop and a follow up e-mail survey (Annex VI) to be sent after the workshop.

Reporting

Section G briefly describes how each workshop will be reported for the analysis of its results through a reporting template (Annex VII).

A.5 Assistance and support

Organising the Consultation Workshop will be a challenging but hopefully rewarding task. However, NHCs will not be alone. We hope this Manual will help you guiding through the whole process, but if you have any questions or doubts, do not hesitate to contact us!

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RECRUITMENT

B. Recruitment

The purpose of this section is to help NHCs identify and mobilize representatives of each stakeholder group within their hub area for the M9-M10 Consultation Workshop.

This section includes the following subsections: Recruitment criteria, Rationale for participating, Invitations, and Information package and previous work, as well as annexes with the Stakeholders mapping tables (Annex I), an Invitation letter template (Annex II) and an Information package (Annex III).

The five groups of stakeholders specifically considered in the project are:

- **Civil Society Organisations** (including foundations, associations, social movements, community based organisations, or charities; it also includes the media);
- **Education community** (both informal and formal, from Ministry to school level);
- **Industry and business representatives** from various fields (with in-house or outsourced innovation departments and/or with some R&I base);
- **Policymakers** (including funding agencies, regulators, and executive);
- **Researchers and innovators** (affiliated with various institutions and organizations on different levels).

Using the Stakeholders mapping tables (Annex I), NHCs will select 3 representatives of each stakeholder group. The workshop should be postponed if fewer than 2 participants from any stakeholder group are confirmed.

B.1 Recruitment criteria

As a whole, the group of attendees should meet certain criteria listed as follows:

Table B.1. Overall group composition criteria

Demographics	15 people ($\pm 1-2$) ¹
	even balance of gender
	geographical variety (cities/regions/countries – for multinational hubs)
Expertise	3 people per stakeholder group ²
	good mix of sectors (public, private, non-profit, inside/outside academia...)
	similar level (all have something at stake with at least one RRI aspect)
	balance between naive, enthusiastic individuals (open to changes) and ‘old regime’, powerful individuals (reluctant to change)

¹ If a NHC considers essential inviting more than 17 people, then two workshops should be run in parallel, which means doubling all the requested human and material resources detailed in this Manual.

² Exceptionally, a minimum of 2 or a maximum of 4 people for a specific group could be accepted. However, this should not be the norm. The workshop should be postponed if fewer than 2 participants are confirmed for any stakeholder group.

To accomplish the workshop goals, participants should be carefully selected attending to the needs of the promising practices collection and the stakeholder consultation.

NHCs should identify organisations that are relevant actors in RRI. Of course, probably some of them will already be the Hub members that you have been recruiting during these months. Going further, the Stakeholder mapping (Annex I) identifies the profiles of these organizations and individuals that are target users of the RRI Toolkit and, thus, potential participants of the workshop. Each individual will not necessarily represent only one group, but may be well positioned to represent one or several groups' views.

If NHCs experience difficulties to reach some of the stakeholder groups, they can request help from the project partners, especially from the networks (Bonn Science Shop -CIPAST-, Ecsite, European Business Network -EBN-, European Foundation Centre -EFC-, European Schoolnet -EUN-, and EuroScience), which are European wide and can help NHCs to contact with some of their members in a given country/region. Some of these networks were also the stakeholder group leaders that performed the mapping under WP2; do not hesitate to contact them if you think they can help you (see [message in Basecamp](#)).

Alternatively, NHCs could start with an initial list of potential candidates and ask them for further individual recommendations ('snowball' recruitment).

Attendees should be individuals who, according to NHCs judgment, are influential, informed, accessible, and able to act as agents of change, as detailed in Table B.2.

Table B.2. Ideal characteristics of the workshop attendees

Influential	Representatives in terms of their official position
	Advocates of the group they represent
	Experts in their specific field in terms of practice
Informed	Aware of the grand societal challenges ³ and of ways to address them
Accessible & agents of change	Not so low in the social/administrative ladder so they cannot perform changes, but not so high they cannot commit to fully attend the workshop and further collaborate with the project

B.2 Rationale for participating

The challenges of this consultation are many: it must consider a wide range of stakeholder profiles, each playing a different but related role in the RRI process. It must also be applicable in a wide range of settings across the 19 hubs of the project. Finally, each stakeholders group has its own specific issues, interests and needs.

Before contacting any of the stakeholders who could potentially attend the workshop, NHCs will need to have a first idea of what are their interests and concerns regarding RRI and related topics. The following rationale proposes an overview of some of the potential issues that may arise during the recruitment process and the consultation. Section B.2.1 describes some general considerations that NHCs will have

³ By grand societal challenges we mean those of the Horizon 2020 (secure, clean and efficient energy; sustainable transport; public health, demographic change and wellbeing; climate action, environment and resources; sustainable food and water; social inclusion, innovation and reflection; security).

to keep in mind to attract potential candidates to the workshop, while Sections B.2.2-B.2.6, organized per stakeholder group, may help in identifying the specific opportunities and issues of each group. In addition, NHCs may think on other aspects not considered here or specific to their region. This rationale can, therefore, be used as part of the dialogue with the stakeholders for organising the workshop (meetings, invitations, e-mails and other forms of communication), adjusting these approaches to each hub context.

This section is an adaptation of the “Guidelines for the implementation of the stakeholder consultation in relation to RRI” ([Deliverable 2.1](#)), which we strongly recommend for reading, plus feedback gathered from individual contributions and the Copenhagen Consortium Meeting (M6).

B.2.1 General considerations

The first questions that NHCs will have to face from the candidates are probably ‘Why should I care about RRI’ and ‘Why should I attend your workshop?’. Depending on their interests, it is clear that some candidates will be actively pushing for RRI and participation in the workshop and others will be mostly pulled. However, and no matter how much they all agree on the need to align research and social interests, attendees will need to see returning benefits to attend a whole-day event that may in some cases force them to travel considerable distances. Table B.3 summarizes some general benefits for them.

Table B.3. General benefits for the workshop participants

<p>Be aware, be funded</p>	<p>RRI is a cross-cutting issue at the European Commission Horizon 2020 Framework Programme. Being aware and informed on RRI, and participating in the RRI movement and the RRI Tools CoP will help stakeholders to propose projects with the adequate RRI focus and boost their chances to access EU’s funds.</p>
<p>Sparkle future collaborations</p>	<p>The workshop is only the first step in a fruitful collaboration with RRI Tools in general and some of Consortium members in particular. It is thus an opportunity to expand the stakeholder’s institution connections and projects at the national and European levels.</p>
<p>Be the spearhead of the RRI movement</p>	<p>By participating in the workshop, the CoP and the future project events the stakeholder will become part of the emerging RRI movement in her/his region, with the possibility of influencing future directions for policy making on RRI, opportunities of funding, being seen from the EU as a leading institution in your region, etc.</p>
<p>Play your part in the Community of Practice</p>	<p>The stakeholder will become part of the CoP, which will allow her/his institution to network with other potential partners in their region, to find European partners for EU calls, to be updated on what is going on about RRI, to be heard and influence on the Toolkit development, to add promising RRI practices, to take part in training events on the RRI Toolkit and RRI advocacy workshops, to share and discover existing tools, to exchange experiences on how to put RRI into practice, etc.</p>
<p>Speak up and be listened</p>	<p>The stakeholder’s institution views and all the workshop outcomes will be analyzed and taken into account to design and develop tailor-made tools that help stakeholders incorporate and promote RRI in their current work. The workshop goes well beyond an academic reflection on barriers and needs and should provide key insights (solutions) into how the Toolkit will be developed to address the stakeholder needs. RRI Tools, funded with 7 M€, is one of the European Commission key projects on RRI. Its Toolkit and outcomes have thus a great chance to influence EC’s future policies and, in turn, national ones.</p>

**Be visible,
be published**

RRI Tools will offer visibility to the stakeholder's institution through its dissemination channels, events organised by the NHCs, reports, deliverables, publications, etc.

Additionally, the RRI practices provided by the stakeholders will be analysed and, when considered relevant enough, incorporated in the Promising Practices Collection published on the RRI Tools website as part of the Toolkit.

Among all these practices, a set will be chosen as the 10 Best Practices. For these practices, RRI Tools will contact a prestigious journal on responsible research and innovation to publish them in it.

B.2.2 Civil Society Organizations (CSOs)

Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) constitute a stakeholder group usually eager to share their own opinions and practical experience on societal problems with a range of stakeholders, able to offer new perspectives by representing silent voices, and often with more available time than other groups. However, many CSOs are tired of consultations that discuss their concerns without providing solutions.

Therefore, interests of CSOs should be aligned with those of responsible research and innovation. This means:

More engagement of CSOs in science through involvement in research agenda setting

CSOs are extremely underrepresented in committees for science policy and decision-making, and as such have only little or no influence. Research and innovation must understand the views of CSOs and the way these impact research agendas. This includes the need to share models of good practices across Europe.

Acknowledgement of CSO knowledge and expertise outside the formal research system

Civil society needs to be recognised as a producer of knowledge, and CSOs have to be accepted as partners in research and innovation directed towards public interest. Today there is some interest in participation of citizens and CSOs in community-based research, policy processes and decision-making. However, there is still a long way to go before citizens and CSOs are fully accepted as equal partners and providers of knowledge and expertise to solve societal challenges.

CSOs have valuable expertise and often enjoy close links with the people most likely to benefit from research. For their part, most researchers want the knowledge they generate to benefit society.

Getting free (open) access to research results

Open Science, Open Access strategies and Knowledge Commons should be applied. The decisions on priority setting of research agendas and the composition of steering committees of research institutions are not transparent enough, also because science policy and governance get low public attention. This is an obstacle for democratic decision-making about priorities and aims of research that should be oriented at societal problems and should help prepare solutions.

Simultaneously the need for publication often inhibits CSOs involvement in research, given that CSOs are usually focused on managing or giving solutions to societal problems without taking part in the academic publication system.

Create support mechanisms and research funding schemes for CSOs

How can research funders across Europe support publicly engaged research and joint research projects with CSOs? This has an implication on the levels of understanding of research partnerships amongst research funders, and that is why CSOs must be involved in this process. There is an emerging interest in examining and spreading out models of good practice in research with and for CSOs.

Overcome the negative perception of CSOs in the research system

The role of CSOs in research projects is perceived very differently by academic institutions and by the CSOs themselves. This reflects a tendency among project coordinators to attribute a more passive role to CSO participants, who in turn feel their voices are not weighted evenly as those of their research partners. Academic partners value CSOs participation insofar as it facilitates dissemination of results and helps test developments, but they often miss that contact with CSOs at research institutions can increase mutual understanding and foster synergies between both stakeholder groups.

B.2.3 Education community

The education community seek to educate citizens with solid arguments and inspire future researchers on science-society issues and, thus, ensure their activities are aligned with the latest European priorities and increase their impact. In this respect, RRI may offer an opportunity to let students understand societal challenges from a different perspective, make classical science more meaningful and closer to their daily life, include social sciences in the big picture, and close the gap between education centres and other stakeholders, such as CSOs, policymakers and the industry and business sector.

Nevertheless, some aspects of RRI are already familiar to this stakeholder group and have been put in practice for decades. On the other hand, there are some general issues for formal and informal education sectors that have to be kept in mind when talking to members of this group.

Additionally, needs and concerns of formal/informal and primary & secondary/tertiary education sectors may differ significantly, and thus an adequate coverage of all these subgroups should be sought for the workshop.

Unclear understanding of RRI concept in the education sector

RRI is a new term and the fact that there is no clear understanding of RRI yet makes it difficult to create appropriate tangible and specific programmes and activities that reflect the term. Transferring the term into activities for educators is an important issue.

Educators need a definition of RRI that is adjusted to their work and to their audiences. For informal education, they need a definition that they can work with easily when they develop education activities for young people, families or adults. Science centres and museums are picking up the idea and have started to organise an increasing number of activities that are exploring issues around RRI. In formal education, the aim is to make sure the STEM curriculum can contribute to make research and innovation responsible and provide teachers the necessary tools to educate students in that perspective.

Current lack of evaluation framework for RRI activities

Since RRI is a relatively new activity for education organisations, learning institutions need an evaluation framework that can be applied to RRI activities. Measuring impact is an issue in general for science centres and museums when it comes to 'proving' their value, because traditional indicators used in assessing learning do not apply in any case to the sector.

The link between the mission of informal learning institutions and RRI is not clear

The mission of many informal learning institutions is very often linked to making young people enthusiastic about science. The motto that science is fun and exciting can be contradictory to what RRI is advocating for. Science centres and museums must be open to a more neutral role for them when it comes to the value of science and technology. There is a need to propose a set of values that represent RRI so that science centres and museums can explore how these values match their missions.

The role of informal learning institutions towards RRI is not recognised enough

Informal learning organisations do have connections with the industry sector, governance and research, but mostly with regards to education related activities. There is still road ahead until informal learning organisations have a well-defined role in RRI processes, at least on a national and regional level. Hence, museums need to develop their connections with more diverse departments of universities and research institutes and advocate their role in RRI more strongly. Being part of this workshop is an opportunity to develop such connections.

The RRI concept is not included in most European curricula

The concept of RRI has not yet been introduced in the formal education sector. Many outreach activities for schools have been implemented to engage students and teachers on Science in Society issues and Ethical, Legal and Social aspects of Science. However, few outreach and research actions have been undertaken to tackle the additional dimensions introduced by the RRI concept.

Hence, ministries of education need to be informed of the concept of RRI and the need to include pedagogical objectives and activities that will contribute to RRI in the STEM curriculum at primary, secondary and tertiary levels, probably as a transversal topic.

Teachers need to be familiarised and trained with the methods and tools that will prepare students to contribute to RRI as well, integrating and teaching RRI in a concrete way through the use of role-play, case-based learning. Also a multiplying effect among teachers is needed to spread the concept and teaching methods. In the end the aims are to prepare students to take part to the public debate related to research and innovation, to raise their interest for scientific careers, and to teach STEM including the 'responsible' dimension.

The education community is not engaged in R&I processes sufficiently

Schools, industry and research institutes are still not well connected and teachers and students are therefore not included in the research and innovation process. Participating in this debate and consultation with other stakeholders may lead to a platform for schools, industry and research institutes to collaborate on RRI activities and make teachers feel empowered to be involved in the Research and Innovation process.

Difficulties to implement changes

Teachers may feel very difficult to implement changes to incorporate RRI in their activities, mainly due to their hectic daily schedule, the need to follow the official curricula, and the resistance from managers and colleagues from different fields to scale up and spread the impact of the concept within their own institution.

B.2.4 Industry and business representatives

Industry and business with research and innovation base look for social acceptance of innovation to ensure that the market will not react against an emerging technology and to improve the social perception of their company. In this respect, RRI may offer financing opportunities for future product developments and could foster the conversion of 'traditional' business into more sustainable, open to new markets ones. However, in order to engage industry and business representatives there are some specific issues of this stakeholder group that have to be taken into account.

Priority given to the bottom line

Most innovations that matter are difficult to explain in terms of return on investment, and mostly imply an uncertain investment and time to market that represent a significant challenge for the company's bottom line. Some R&D investments may not pay-off at all.

Opening to RRI and including decision makers in the process of creating new measurements of success will contribute to expand the scope of the success of innovations; it is often possible to avoid a narrow look to short-term profits. However transparency issues may arise, since property rights and confidentiality are a key source of competitive advantages.

Lack of (collective) incentives for responsible research and innovation

Taking into consideration their institutional role of maximising profit, companies have no incentive to undertake responsible research and innovation, especially when comparing the costs of transforming a company into an RRI one with those of competitors without the need to accomplish that transformation. Participation on the public debate around RRI will help create a common awareness of the problems placed by irresponsible research and innovation and understand future scenarios and potential societal reactions.

Market failures and negative social returns

As the results of production are not directly realised, managers and consumers do not have the incentive -or do not recognise the need for- more responsible research and innovation activities and results. There is a need to translate into business terms what is the advantage of applying RRI criteria to Research and Innovation to avoid adopting just cosmetic measurements that may limit RRI to a simple marketing strategy.

Involving industry in the debate with other RRI stakeholders will help to produce recommendations to policymakers, insofar as they should shape the market so that RRI is rewarded.

Technological lock-in

Innovations, including responsible innovations, face a number of barriers to take-up. Educators and other stakeholders have a high level of awareness of how these barriers refer to innovation as a whole. For industry stakeholders, participating in a wide debate on RRI will help to increase this awareness and seek effective solutions.

There is a need to create specific market niches where new technologies can benefit from learning opportunities. This can happen, for example, in pilot projects in RRI.

B.2.5 Policymakers

The engagement of this particular group of stakeholders, key for the success of the project and of RRI in general, involves a number of critical issues that must be carefully addressed. A good strategy might be to start inviting the policymakers who have been engaged with some aspect of RRI to begin with (e.g., science and society, gender, public inclusion, public engagement).

Unfamiliarity/lack of understanding of the issue

Many policymakers, particularly those working outside the science and society agenda, are unlikely to be familiar with the term or some of the issues that comprise the concept, and also unlikely to understand why it is important or useful to them. This requires a clear explanation and compelling argument of why RRI will help policymakers (e.g., RRI involves engaging the public in meaningful ways, which could help bring people closer to politics).

Democratic deficit

Policymakers (especially elected politicians) see a gap between public and politics. In addressing this gap, they are keen to talk about issues that people can relate to. Science might not be seen as such an issue. This requires showing policymakers how RRI is not just talking about abstract scientific research, but that it also relates to things that people care about, such as healthcare, energy prices, and other societal issues. In this respect, focusing on improving the acceptance of emerging technologies may be more engaging for them.

Also RRI can ensure that research and innovation works better for society, giving more power to citizens and offering a chance for politicians to be on the side of the public.

Economic constraints

Anything that will be seen as inhibiting the role of science as a driver of the economy – or its ability to produce economic benefits, growth, and jobs – will be resisted, as will anything that appears to make a country less competitive than others. Therefore, it is important to put forward the argument that economic benefits will be constrained if science is rejected by public, and that a significant range of stakeholders depend on the investment on research and innovation. RRI is a key way to develop science with and for society and therefore maximise economic benefits.

As a complementary reason for engagement, emphasizing solutions that require low budget is critical to gain the confidence of this group; funding is based on those who provide the best solutions for a given budget. Cooperation measurements, for example, can be feasibly promoted by policymakers.

Lack of time

Engaging policymakers with issues around RRI might be difficult, especially if this matter is outside their 'core' function. Make sure RRI is presented as relevant to core policy issues by identifying current local policy issues that have links to different dimensions of RRI. Show how participation in the workshop is as time effective as possible and contributes to policymakers core functions, as well as to our interests (e.g., providing networking opportunities).

Compliance with legal requirements sufficient

For some policymakers complying with legal requirements around equality and responsibility (for instance) will be seen as sufficient to fulfil their role. RRI does not seem to cover any additional needs. Further, support from its institution is key and, though there might be a strong European push on RRI and a global movement in research governance, national policymakers may not react till direct pressure is put on them.

Examples on how to incorporate RRI through national funding programmes may help to bridge this gap.

B.2.6 Researchers and innovators

However odd it may sound, this group of stakeholders might be one of the most resistant to engage in the RRI Tools discussion because of a number of concerns summarized below.

Am I not responsible?

Researchers may feel they are blamed for not being responsible. Clarifying this concern and explaining how RRI looks for a shared responsibility and promotes their contribution as researchers to the social impact of their work through inclusion and to promote a better image of science through openness (which both may help in obtaining more funds and making science sustainable) may be reassuring.

Collaboration with other stakeholders may also provide a better understanding and new ways of looking at their own research and its impact, as well as ease the social acceptance of their fieldwork.

Should I be responsible?

Some researchers may think that it is not their responsibility what happens with their research out of the academia, laboratory, etc., or that it is not their job doing consultations or public engagement. Examples of technology acceptance issues and of the impact that distorted images offered to the public by non-expert voices have on some research areas may help in showing how this 'scientist in the ivory tower' idea is not adequate to present times.

Researchers need also to realize that voicing their opinions to policymakers (including the European Commission) is a key way to secure the future of their own research.

Finally researchers from some fundamental research areas may object that they cannot do science for society, but only for basic knowledge. This is absolutely reasonable and RRI does not have to affect all research areas.

Lack of time and rewards

Research career is mainly based on publishing and, within the academia, on teaching. To these priorities researchers have to add a considerable amount of time dealing with the R&I bureaucratic system (calls for funding, project management, report writing, securing a tenure position, applying for promotions, etc.). Adding another task to their to-do list may be seen like a burden to the ever-increasing demands on researchers more than an opportunity.

In addition, researchers may not see any direct reward in implementing RRI. Working in a system that does not even reward outreach and public engagement efforts, only individuals personally committed to the RRI ideals will engage with them, especially when there is no system in place to evaluate RRI. In this respect, funding calls that specifically devote part of the budget to RRI may be a way to encourage researchers to apply the RRI principles.

Freedom of research and concerns about bureaucracy

Freedom of research is essential to scientific progress. Researchers may feel inclusion of different stakeholders (especially policymakers and civil society) as interference on their work: research, after all, should be a matter for researchers. This can be replied with the idea that research is too important for our society and that it has too often unexpected consequences as to not share responsibility among all stakeholders.

Also researchers do not need a new report template sheet to fill up. We should avoid inappropriate bureaucracy that puts obstacles to researchers to go ahead with their research. Will RRI drive us to add a new checklist to the existing ones? This should be avoided at all costs. If RRI becomes a requirement, researchers may have the feeling they are being imposed some kind of useless and time-wasting task. In this sense, researchers may end up thinking that RRI is only about ticking another checklist while keep doing business as usual.

Unfamiliarity with RRI

Research institutions and funders are more likely to have leverage on several of the RRI components (open access, ethics, science education) than other groups, but being RRI an emerging idea, they may first encounter difficulties in fully assimilating the concept. This requires showing the relevance and importance of RRI, of training (as conceived in the 'train the trainers' programme for M24+), of simple and practical tools (as planned in the Toolkit), and of taking under consideration cultural differences and national policies. It also requires tying RRI to ordinary actions in research, instead of presenting it separated from these actions.

Lack of leverage

On an individual level, researchers may have the feeling they cannot change anything, or so little, on their own and that they may not receive support from their institution. This requires participatory governance as well as an increased involvement of researchers in decision making.

This situation may require the involvement/creation of new management staff positions to assist researchers and support the implementation of RRI. However, this may also result in an RRI manager/department that bears sole responsibility on its application, which would contradict the concept of RRI.

RRI is an heterogeneous concept

The concept of RRI, from the point of view of some scientists, mixes unrelated issues and lacks a common, unifying concept. Hence, for the target group 'individual researchers', RRI issues should be addressed separately and not under a common 'RRI' heading, which is more adapted to an institutional framework, such as research organizations and funders.

B.3 Invitations

Direct contact (phone calls, meetings, etc.) with chosen candidates before sending them a formal invitation to the workshop will certainly help to obtain positive responses. Once this first contact has been successful, a formal invitation should be sent to confirm attendance. These invitations to the workshop should be sent well in advance (at least 6-8 weeks, better before the end of July -M7-) to ensure the availability of the chosen candidates. Try to contact/invite 4 or more representatives of each stakeholder group to anticipate refusals. The process may need several rounds of invitations to secure the minimum number of 3 representatives per stakeholder group is reached (see B.1).

Annex II offers a template for an invitation/save-the-date e-mail that should be adapted by each NHC for its own national/regional particularities, including date and time of the workshop.

Invitations should provide a short summary of the project, as well as basic dissemination material (web and social media links, digital leaflet, see C.1). Additionally, they should make clear that the workshop is only the initial point in building a wide Community of Practice, and that participating in it will allow attendees to become the nucleus of this CoP in their area of influence (see B.2).

Follow-up calls should be planned 10 days after the invitation was sent, in order to increase the response rate. The week before the workshop take place, last minute check should be performed.

Invited candidates who cannot finally attend the workshop will be asked to participate in a short e-mail survey (Annex VI) circulated after the event, and will receive details on how to engage with the project further in the future.

B.4 Information package and previous work from participants

In order to make the Consultation Workshop successful, good preparation of the participants is crucial. Participants should know beforehand about the topic and content of the workshop and have a clear idea of what is expected from them.

Therefore, once potential candidates confirm their attendance to the workshop, they should receive an e-mail with extra information regarding the event. This e-mail should contain the Information package (Annex III), which consists of four different documents:

- RRI information sheet;
- Examples of promising RRI practices;
- Promising practice question sheet (part A);⁴
- Informed consent form.

In the text of the e-mail participants should be requested to read carefully the RRI information sheet (where it is stated what we mean by RRI) and the examples provided of promising RRI practices, and then to fill in the promising practice question sheet (part A) in preparation to the workshop. The e-mail text should also explain that filling in the sheet will only take a couple of minutes and that the discussions during the workshop will tremendously gain in richness and depth if the participants bring an example of a promising practice.

⁴ Note that Annex III contains both part A and B of the promising practice question sheet. Make sure you only send part A of this question sheet, since part B (which needs more time than part A) is only for being filled by participants during the workshop.

The question sheet requires the participants to provide a brief description of a promising RRI practice that they were involved in or they know it took place in their region/country⁵. The description should be made along the lines of the question sheet and be provided to the NHC prior to the workshop.

The e-mail text should also ask participants to read the informed consent carefully, so they can quickly sign a hardcopy of it at the beginning of the workshop. This document has to answer the following considerations:

- What the project and the workshop are (purpose, duration, and aims);
- Confidentiality and data/pictures treatment;
- Contact for rights and claims;
- Voluntary participation.

Annex III provides an informed consent template for the Consultation Workshop where detailed answers to the above mentioned questions are given to ensure that the rights of each participant are respected. NHCs should adapt this template to their own language and particularities of their regional area of influence, and keep the signed hard copies along with the rest of project documents.

Finally, the e-mail should provide practicalities, such as:

- Agenda of the workshop;
- Address of the meeting place and how to get there, including parking options;
- Hotel address (if required);
- Contact phone numbers and e-mail addresses;
- Tourist map of town;
- Other local necessities each workshop may require.

One week before the workshop NHCs should send to participants a reminder of the event as well as a request to them to send back the Promising RRI practice question sheet (part A) (Annex III) filled in.

⁵ Since the Consultation Workshop aims to collect promising RRI practices from all regions across Europe, it is expected that participants provide examples from their own region/country. NHCs could exceptionally accept an example from a different country, but it should not be the norm.

DISSEMINATION

C. Dissemination plan

Organizing the workshops across Europe is a way to raise awareness of RRI and RRI Tools locally, both:

- Directly towards the invited stakeholders, who are the first members of the Community of Practice; and
- Indirectly through social media and press relations.

Here are a few recommendations you are invited to follow before, during and after the workshop to spread awareness of RRI Tools and engage more stakeholders to join the conversation.

C.1 Before the workshop

Please **inform EuroScience of the date of the event no later than 6 weeks in advance**, so that communication can be planned accordingly.

The next step is to send invitations 6-8 weeks before the event and to plan follow-up calls 10 days after the message is sent.

Remember to keep a list of all the people you invite with all relevant data. Make sure to collect their contact details and, if possible, social media contacts and e-mails/phone numbers.

Regarding the **project's communication strategy**, the invitation should contain dissemination materials, such as the [leaflet](#) (ideally adapted to your local language using the leaflet [template](#) and [text in English](#) for translation) and a link to the [website](#) and all the project's social media accounts ([Twitter](#), [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#)). Also invite recipients to join the RRI Tools database [through our website](#) and to follow/join us on social media.

Prepare in advance the promotional material of your institution (roll-ups, flyers, goodies, etc.) and of RRI Tools (leaflets, roll-ups, A3 posters) that will be displayed in the workshop room. As stated above, the RRI Tools [leaflet](#) (in English) and the leaflet [template](#) (to adapt in other languages and print) are already available on Basecamp. You will be provided in Basecamp by end of July with 2 extra template versions you are free to edit in your local language and to print by your own means:

- One for the roll-up, and
- One for the A3 poster.

Please take into account that when specific material has to be produced you will need to start several weeks before to be on time: four weeks is usually a minimum. If you were in need of extra material or you would like to produce new materials, please get in touch with EuroScience (Alexia Harambure: alexia.harambure@euroscience.org) at least four weeks before.

A **press release** should be sent to journalists to make them aware of the workshop. It should be brief and answer the following questions: what is it about? Who is it for? Where and when does it take place? How does it work? Who is organizing it? It should end with the details of a contact person in your institution. EuroScience will share in Basecamp by the end of July a template of press release to be locally adapted. Ideally, **the press release should be sent 15 days before the workshop (one month and a half before, if it is a monthly magazine)**. This timing may depend on local contexts, so phoning back journalists a few days afterwards is often necessary to get feedback and know if they will tackle your activity.

Publish posts on social media announcing your workshop, making sure you mention RRI Tools to ease the echoing and the follow-up (i.e., using [@RRITools](#) on Twitter, mentioning [RRI Tools](#) in Facebook and publishing in the LinkedIn [discussion group](#)). Post updates about the workshop on your website and integrate the information in your institution's newsletter. Ask your networks to disseminate the information on their own communication channels as well, incorporating workshop references into their website, social media posts, public calendar of events, etc.

C.2 During the workshop

During the workshop **take photos and publish posts on social media that convey what is happening**, the general atmosphere. Whenever possible include photos, audio or video files in your posts on social media to raise the attention of your audience and make the news more appealing.

As well, along the whole workshop try to **reinforce the message to the participants to use our website, sign-up to the database and follow us in social media**, making sure you mention it in the introduction to the project (Session 1), and before participants leave at the end of the workshop. If possible, collect social media contacts as well as e-mails/phone numbers. Make clear that the objective of this follow up is to keep in touch with them, send them information (both on the project – outcomes, activities, etc. – and about RRI in general); as well, invite them to be 'interactive' with us, stating that we need to receive their input, ideas, criticisms, etc. Basically the idea we have to convey is that we are building a European Community of Practice, that from the moment they participate in the workshop they are part of this community, and that our aim is to keep together the community lively and growing.

At the end of the day **make sure participants fill in the evaluation questionnaire** (Annex V), giving them enough time to do so before leaving.

C.3 After the workshop

After the workshop **follow up the contacts you made**, try to keep them active in relation to the project and address them with relevant news and updates; as well, try to channel them to the main communication tools of the project (website, social media).

While you produce the workshop report (Annex VII), you can try to write a **short, general chronicle** of how it was. You can use a more informal style, narrating how the experience was both for organizers and participants, conveying the main discussions or outcomes, subjective impressions, adding verbatim comments etc. A piece like this, of about 8-10 lines, can be **later used to feed the RRI Tools blog** (currently under construction), **to produce contents for social media, a press release, etc.**

Post on the social media, newsletter and website (of your institution and of RRI Tools) information on the outcomes of the workshop, such as a general chronicle talking about the participants, their general impressions on the workshop, the impact of their feedback on the RRI Toolkit, next steps regarding the RRI Toolkit...).

A press release about the outcomes of the workshop should be sent to specialized journalists as soon as possible after the workshop with the same kind of information – number of attendees, global atmosphere, general conclusions and impacts in the future –, following the same steps described for the press release in section C.1.

Contents of the evaluation (section F and Annex V) and the workshop report (section G and Annex VII) will be used for the deliverable D6.6, a global report about all the events RRI Tools has organized and taken part to, to be handed out at the end of the project (M36).

STAFF COMPETENCES, SKILLS AND DUTIES

D. Staff competences, skills, and duties

The success of the Consultation Workshop strongly depends on the ability of the host (NHC) to set up the logistics appropriately and of the moderator to conduct the event smoothly to accomplish each session goals. For this purpose, chapter D reviews the skills and tasks expected for the host organization, the moderator and related staff.

Each workshop has to be hosted by one moderator and one assistant. The moderator will lead through the workshop according to the structure outlined in sections E.1 to E.4. The assistant will support the moderator throughout the workshop by:

- Assisting participants when they arrive, at breaks and lunch, and when they leave;
- Distributing required materials (stationery, questionnaires, etc.);
- Leading groups to other rooms, if needed;
- Conducting the exercises;
- Taking notes and pictures;
- Taking care of the documentation for reporting (see Section G) and attendance.

It is highly recommendable that both the moderator and the assistant are part of the NHC organization and are already working in RRI Tools, as significant – but tacit- knowledge will emerge from the group dynamics that can prove useful for the NHC and the project. However, if NHCs feel they lack the staff to perform these tasks, they may consider hiring a skilled professional for the moderation (given that the allocated budget for the NHC allows this option).

Similarly, since background information about RRI should be provided to the participants before discussing their needs and constraints, contributions from external invited experts or other stakeholders during Session 2 can be taken into account.

D.1 Building on group interaction

The concepts that will be discussed in the workshops are social constructs. Views, opinions, ideas and concerns are heavily dependent on the personal, historical and cultural context in which we live and work. Also the way we talk about our values and beliefs is highly complex. This talk is relationally structured, which means that the beliefs that we express are all interrelated and dependent on one another in some way. The meaning of values, beliefs and concerns does not reside as some kind of mental entity in our mind, but is actively negotiated and constructed during the course of conversation. The workshops should be recognized as sites of social interaction through which meaning and understanding are co-constructed. Group interaction thus forms a crucial part of the research process.

So, moderators work with groups. The dynamics of each group will greatly influence the nature of the discussion and the results. The success of group work depends on the ability of the moderator, supported by the format of questions and exercises, to manage these dynamics. Groups tend to behave like one large organism: every member influences each other. A group is always inclined to reach an equilibrium state. The members of the group play different roles, which can be both facilitating and hindering communication. As a moderator, you should know how to handle these actions and roles to structure the discussion towards the aspired aim.

Different factors affect group dynamics. First of all there are intra- and interpersonal characteristics, such as personality and group compatibility. Second, there are environmental factors, such as the

material environment and the spatial arrangements. Of course, the Consultation Workshop is a once-only event. Still, specific interaction patterns will emerge between participants. Some will be likely to add on each other’s ideas (complementary interaction). Others will be likely to criticize each other’s ideas (competitive interaction). The challenge for the moderator is to mobilize these interaction patterns in such a way that all participants feel comfortable and contribute to the eventual result. Section D.2 addresses how moderators can take up this challenge.

D.2 Moderator competencies

As a moderator, you have crucial role in the workshop discussion: your role is to maintain the focus of the discussion. After all, in 6-7 hours enough material should have been collected to contribute significantly to the workshop objectives. Maintaining the focus implies making sure that the key themes are covered while managing group dynamics. Your role is to guide and stimulate the discussion. You facilitate the discussion using the script (Annex IV) with all the questions and exercises to guide and ensure equal individual input as well as group discussion. You should also create an open and safe environment so people feel encouraged and free to speak up and be actively involved in the discussion.

You can imagine yourself as the conductor of an orchestra: you will obtain the workshop objectives by getting the best out of every participant.

The competencies that you should have, as a moderator, to fulfil these roles can be divided into those for interpersonal communication, process management, and understanding, as shown in Table D.1.

Table D.1. Most important competencies of the moderator

Category	Competency	Explanation
Interpersonal communication	Perceptive listening	Using sensing and intuition to elicit cognitive and emotive meanings
	Verbal and nonverbal speaking	Clear and unambiguous use of words, language, tone, posture, and signs
	Sensitivity	Openness to generate empathic understanding of individual and group needs
	Trustworthiness	Can gain high levels of trust from individuals and the group
Process management	Lead the group	Flexible in working with the group and adopting both directive and facilitative leadership styles
	Challenging	Stretch and challenge the group. Encourage creativity without losing safety
	Modelling neutrality	Postpone judgment and demonstrate interest in all contributions offered
	Conflict resolution	Resolve challenging conflicts
Understanding	Intellectual agility	Thinking on your feet; assimilate information quickly and conceptual flexibility
	Helicopter view	See connections between statements and the whole
	Reflexive awareness	Recognizing underlying values and beliefs in uttered statements
	Self-awareness	Reflection on the influence of own role on group dynamics and the ability to adapt

D.3 Moderator skills

As a small group discussion moderator you need a specific selection of facilitation skills, which can be grouped in four areas: listening, positive accepting, process interventions, and dealing with resistance.

D.3.1 Listening

During a group discussion the aim is to understand what participants really think of a certain subject. Therefore, the information you collect should be framed in the participants' own language, concepts and understanding of the world. It is important to minimize the influence of your own views and understandings of the world. Therefore, it is crucial to listen without judgment or filters. Furthermore, you do not only want to hear what a certain participant thinks, but also gain in-depth understanding of the arguments why that participant thinks in that way. Small group discussions are all about exploring the underlying reasons for certain views, opinions or ideas. A highly effective way to achieve this in collecting responses in a group discussion is the *LSC procedure* (Listen, Summarize, Clarify), summarized in Table D.2.

Table D.2. LSC procedure

Listen	Carefully to what a participant has to say. It is important just to focus on what is said, postponing judgment or critique.
Summarize	What has been said to check whether you have got it. Always let the decision of what a statement means and how it should be put down with the participants.
Clarify	With questions to gain an in-depth understanding of a participant's view. Ask 'get questions' ("what do you mean") and 'why questions' ("why do you think that").

As a group discussion moderator you use different types of listening in order to manage the group process and achieve an understanding of the participants' ideas and concerns. Two of the most needed types of listening are empathic and analytical listening.

One of the most difficult aspects of moderating group discussions is the continuous switch between empathic and analytical listening and back. Empathic listening supports the positive interaction with the participants and helps you to understand their perspectives. Analytical listening helps you to structure what is said and bring it in relation to the workshop objective. Table D.3 contrasts empathic and analytical listening.

Empathic listening is usually contrasted with autobiographic listening, unfortunately the most common form of listening in daily life, in which people listen with the intention to answer, not to understand. Autobiographic listening is accompanied by filtering the information heard through one's own paradigms, aiming at recognizing one's own autobiography in the life of others, projecting one's own experience on the experience of others.

Table D.3 Empathic and analytical listening

Empathic listening	Listening with the sincere intention to understand the other person. Engage in the other’s way of thinking, understanding the other’s frame of reference. “Standing in other people’s shoes”.
Importance	You want to understand how your participants think, framed in their words, language and understanding of the world. Therefore, you need to create a safe and friendly conversation environment in which participants are encouraged to talk about their own ideas and views.
How to	Ask ‘get-questions’: “What do you mean by...”; “could you give an example of...”; “how do you see...”, etc. Open up your body posture, make eye contact, smile.
Analytical listening	Listening in order to structure the information heard, recognizing concepts central to the theme of discussion, establishing connections to what has been said already and the direction in which the conversation should be heading.
Importance	You want to gain an in-depth understanding of the participants’ ideas and perceptions. Therefore, you need to structure what is said to unravel underlying arguments and themes.
How to	Ask questions of clarification: “Why do you think that...”; “is what you have said related to...”, etc. Always let the decision be with the participants. Make drawings, mind maps. Take time.

Not only a balance between empathic and analytical listening is important, also the skill of active listening, as described in Table D.4, largely contributes to the success of a small group discussion.

Table D.4 Active listening

Active listening	Focus on listening rather than talking, treat what is said with care.
Importance	The group discussion is all about the explorations and discussions of the group participants. A moderator should not interrupt or fill in too much, and nurture the generation of ideas amongst the participants instead.
How to	Make a conscious effort to listen. Repeat what is said out loud or in your mind. Open up your body posture, make eye contact, smile.

D.3.2 Positive accepting

A crucial skill of the group discussion moderator is your ability to respond to the participants’ stories in a positive accepting way (Table D.5). This attitude is most important to create a safe and trustworthy environment where participants feel free to express their ideas. Also the positive accepting attitude enables and encourages the creative and constructive flow of ideas.

Table D.5 Positive accepting attitude

Positive accepting attitude	Approaching every idea as a potential contribution to the session output. All ideas are valuable.
importance	Creating a safe and friendly conversational environment. Stimulate the flow of ideas.
how to	Always say 'yes' in your mind to what is brought up. Be aware when to use 'yes-but' responses (aimed at sharpening ideas) and 'yes-and' responses (aimed at building on ideas). Be in the moment. Postpone your judgment. Add to what is there.

As a moderator, your own assumptions, ideas and judgments may hamper your sensitivity and response to what the participants have to say. Accepting what your participants offer, enables you to see the possibilities in their utterances rather than their shortcomings. This will in fact make it easier to manage the group process and to reach your goals. It is not about you or your ego; it is about the collective activity in which the workshop participants are engaged.

D.3.3 Process interventions

It is the task of the group discussion moderator to manage the group process and dynamics. Table D.6 lists several levels of process interventions in the case of group work.

Table D.6 Process interventions

Content	Respond to the content of group work, for example to change the topic, ask for more explanation, etc. Use techniques like summarizing and clarifying participant responses, the clarification of setting and goals or the provision of extra information.
Procedure	Respond to the group process by referring to procedures like the conversation rules, agenda, boundaries, exercises.
Interaction	Respond to the way the participants and the moderator are treating each other and responding to one another by making these interaction patterns explicit or changing your interaction pattern yourself using techniques like sharing concerns of participants, explicitly naming the (obstructive) role of participants in the discussion, explicitly naming the communication pattern from a meta-perspective.
Being	Respond to the way participants are in the group by making that explicit or change your way of being yourself, using techniques like always acknowledge the input of participants, postpone your judgment, show yourself, stimulate openness and respect.

The best way to use these process interventions is situational: skilful moderators are able to switch between the different levels of intervention depending on what the situation needs.

D.3.4 Dealing with resistance

It is the group discussion moderator's task to manage the group process. This means being sensitive to what the group needs. Sometimes you will have to deal with resistance. This is not directly something to worry about. Resistance is just an aspect of group dynamics. Often, participants showing resistance do not do so because they want to undermine your goals, but do so out of insecurity or out of a strong concern for something. This paragraph deals with three types of resistance: repetitive questions, dominance and passivity.

It is very common that participants ask questions to the moderator during the discussion. Of course, it is important that you develop a high level of 'rapport' with your participants in the sense that they understand why they are there, what they have to do and how the roles and responsibilities are distributed. At the same time, questions may disrupt the flow of the discussion or the safety of the conversational environment. Therefore, it is important for a group discussion moderator to respond to questions in a balanced way. Questions can take two forms: about procedures and about content.

Questions about procedures may concern the workshop itself, but also the entire project in which the workshop is situated.

Questions about the nature and background of the project, such as: why are we supposed to do this, who wants to know, who paid for this, might be asked out of curiosity, but may also have something to do with a lack of trust. In the first case, directly postpone these questions to sometime after the sessions. In the latter case, the trust issue is something that you have to deal with right away. Otherwise, the negative attitude of that specific participant may disrupt group dynamics or even spread across the group. Try to establish trust by answering the question as good as possible, being transparent about your role, goals and intentions. Emphasize that you are there to understand how these participants think, in their words and their ways. What they think is important, is important to you too. Tuning in to the participants' feelings and choosing the appropriate response is a matter of experience. The decision between postponing and direct treatment is one you have to make yourself.

Questions may also concern the session itself, the programme and assignments. In this case it is often wise to answer those questions immediately. If you do so, make sure your response is direct and concrete and also to the group as a whole. This way you make sure everybody knows what to do, at the same time avoiding that too much time is spent by you talking and explaining. Furthermore, you turn the focus of the group from one participant's personal needs to the level of the group.

If participants ask questions about assignments that seek a participants' opinion, it is best just to tell them to do the exercise as best as they can. Otherwise, you would pretty soon be filling in what they should be thinking. Sometimes participants can also explicitly ask your opinion on what they wrote. Remember that you are interested in what they think and not in what you as moderator think. In this case it is better just to check that the exercise is well done according to the instructions given. Do not give personal opinions on what participants wrote.

In most cases, the participants of the workshop will be friendly, and willing to cooperate. Occasionally, however, you will run into more problematic behaviour of the participants. The behaviour is problematic in the sense that it obstructs the group process and flow. It can be intentional, but not necessarily. Participants may very well be unaware of the effect of their own behaviour. It can be verbal or nonverbal. It can be directed towards the moderator, or towards the group, or even not directed to anything particular at all. Anyway, the moderator has to deal with it. Often, this kind of behaviour is easy to get round by the use of procedural 'tricks'.

Problematic behaviour can be both of a dominant and passive character (Table D.7).

Table D.7 Problematic behaviours: passivity and dominance

Passivity	A participant drops out of the discussion, sits back, unfocused, and drifts away.
problematic because	Active engagement in the group conversation is important for the workshop results, but also more directly for the group atmosphere. It is the moderator's job to make every participant actively and enthusiastically engaging in the discussions.
Dominance	A participant dominates the conversation, lectures the other participants and obstructs the flow of ideas in all directions
problematic because	Dominance can be produced by overly enthusiasm or aggression. In both cases it creates an unpleasant and hostile atmosphere that inhibits other types of participants to actively participate.

There are very easy-to-install procedural tricks to get round the dominant behaviour of certain participants. Being transparent about your procedures (why you use them) often helps.

A few examples are:

- *Go-rounds*: when asking for participants' opinions or inputs, make a round about the table to let everyone speak. Also, explain to the group that this is the reason why you do it.
- *Write-down exercises*: first let participants think of answers, have them write the answers down, then make a go-round asking them out. This is a very nice way to let every individual have her/his say. Also, you commit participants to what they have written down themselves. If you make go-rounds without write-down, you run the risk of participants being influenced by the dominant, self-assured individual.
- *Respectful parking*: participants can be overly enthusiastic about something that at a particular time is not relevant to the group process. Or a participant can continually be riding her/his hobbyhorse. In those cases you use the empty flipchart (see E.2.2 Session 2 guidelines, Exercise 0) as a virtual parking lot. The 'empty flipchart' can be used as a space for interesting ideas out of the focus of the group work as well. Make sure parking is done with respect, in order to avoid frustration on the side of the participant.
- *Referring to workshop program and procedures*: explaining that there is a time and a place for everything often helps.
- *Direct addressing*: the best way to approach aggressive dominant behaviour is to address it directly and concretely. You will find out that often, if you address the behaviour without judgment, the dominant person will attenuate her/his behaviour. Often dominance will not take a very aggressive form (after all everyone volunteered to participate), but still be disturbing for the process. Usually the other participants will be thankful for your intervention, because they were enduring this aggressive behaviour as well. Try to respond to this behaviour in such a way that the group atmosphere revives the most.

There should be a gradual increase of directness and firmness in your response in relation to the participant's dominant behaviour, as described in Table D.8. It is better to address problematic behaviour in a subtle implicit way, but it is not always enough. Sometimes you have to become explicit or even confronting to regain direction and control.

Your own posture and behaviour can help you enormously in regaining control. Open up, stand up right, express a clear focus to the group or other participants, use your arms to demarcate your focus of attention (even a hand-stop sign can work very elegantly).

Table D.8 Problematic behaviours: steps on the increase in the moderator’s response

Acknowledge & zap	Acknowledge the participant’s input (people want to be heard) but then move on directly to another participant
Summarize & zap	Acknowledge even more by summarizing (making sure that you got it) and then move on to another participant
Explain procedures	Explain that you want to collect the ideas of every participant in the group. Explain that this is why you want everybody to have a say.
Address behavior directly	Describe what you observe. Explain how this interferes with the group process. Ask the participant to adjust behavior.
decision time	For the most dominant participants: there comes a moment that it is ‘change or leave’. Ask the participant why she/he is here. She/he does not have to be here. Make clear that this behavior is not tolerated.

D.4 Further readings

Barbour, R.S. & Kitzinger, J. (1999). *Developing focus group research: politics, theory and practice*. Sage, London.

Greenbaum, T.L. (2000). *Moderating focus groups: a practical guide for group facilitation*. Thousand Oaks, California.

Krueger, R.A. (1994). *Focus groups: a practical guide for applied research*, 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, California.

Litosseliti, L. (2003). *Using focus groups in research*. Continuum, London.

Morgan, D.L. (1997). *Focus groups as qualitative research*, 2nd ed. Sage, London.

SESSION GUIDELINES

E. Session guidelines

The general structure of the workshop, considering a single-day event, is as follows:

Morning	Session 1	Introduction to Workshop and RRI Tools	35'
	Session 2	RRI Working Definition	1h 35' + break times
	Session 3	Compilation of Promising RRI Practices	1h 20' + break times
Lunch			45' - 1h
Afternoon	Session 4	Stakeholder Consultation	3h + break times

Note that there is a logical order to the planning of the activities. The stepwise discussion of the RRI definition, the examples of promising RRI practices and the stakeholder needs and constraints support the exchange of ideas among the participants by gradually moving from general to specific. For an overview of the main goals and outcomes of the whole workshop, see sections A.1 and A.2.

Sections E.1 to E.4 aim at leading the moderators step by step through the whole workshop, with detailed explanations of each session and its corresponding activities. Each session has been designed to offer a set of different techniques and exercises that should best help stimulate and steer discussions and, at the same time, provide structured and visible outcomes.

For the moderator's use in real time during the workshop, the Session Scripts with Guidelines (Annex IV) contain a detailed script and a short briefing for each exercise in the workshop, its objectives, questions to be addressed, timeframe, and material needed.

The proposed methodology can be applied in all countries simply by translating the materials to the local language, but also allows for adaptations in the specific cultural context. Location, time, and hosting facilities can be set according to local habits.

E.1 Session 1: Introduction to Workshop and RRI Tools

E.1.1 Session 1 overview: goals, format, duration, results

Session 1 of the workshop aims to welcome participants, explain some practicalities, provide an introduction to the RRI Tools project, and give an overview of the whole workshop, including the rules of the event.

This introductory session lasts 35 minutes and, though it will not provide tangible outcomes, it is key in creating an open, positive atmosphere for exchanging ideas and to help participants understand the main goals and outcomes of the workshop and the role of participants in the event.

E.1.2 Session 1 guidelines

The following sections are intended to serve as explanations and instructions for the moderator. Annex IV (Session 1) provides the script with guidelines for use in real time during the workshop.

WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION

Objectives

- Give welcome and practical information.
- Registration process.
- Allow participants to get to know each other.
- Provide an introduction of the RRI Tools project.
- Ensure participants understand the structure and objectives of the workshop.
- Create a climate of open exchange.

The moderator and the assistant must start creating an open, friendly atmosphere of exchange from the very beginning. The participants are welcomed to the workshop and asked to fill in the participants list (Annex VIII) and sign the informed consent, which they should have received and read in advance (see B.4).

For the assessment of the needs and constraints of each stakeholder group during Session 4, when doing the registration participants are also asked to define themselves according to one of the groups (civil society organisations, education community, industry and business, policymakers, researchers) using a coloured name badge or by putting a coloured sticky dot on their name tag. This does not contradict the recruitment criteria (see B.2), but gives participants the opportunity to act as representatives of several stakeholder groups based on their experience, if appropriate.

Both the moderator and the assistant present during the workshop are introduced. The moderator explains some practicalities and asks participants for permission to audio-record the workshop and use the data.

The participants are asked to briefly introduce themselves.

An ice-breaker may be used for this introduction (local adaptations and/or playful approach possible, use of icebreakers, etc.).

The moderator then explains the workshop rules and gives a short introduction to the RRI Tools project supported by a PowerPoint presentation. This introduction lets the participants know what is the importance of the project within the RRI context, what are the main goals and outcomes of the project, and what are some of the future actions of the project (including further collaborations with the workshop participants). The presentation provides participants with a general framework to inform them why are they here and what is the project looking for.

For this purpose a few examples of possible tools are provided. The moderator has to emphasize that many more tools are possible to avoid narrowing the term 'tool' and further discussions on it during the workshop.

Finally, the moderator briefly explains what is the overall structure of the whole Consultation Workshop to inform participants on the successive steps (sessions) during the event and presents the main goals and outcomes expected from the consultation, and how they relate to the overall project.

This is the key part of Session 1 and the previous introduction to the project is focused to help participants understand what is stated here: their role in the workshop and their expected contributions.

Participants have to finish Session 1 with the clear idea that we expect from them:

- To be part of the Community of Practice and keep collaborating with RRI Tools;
- To contribute to the working definition of RRI;
- To focus on solutions, not just problems/barriers;
- To provide promising RRI practices, needs and constraints that help shape tools:

PROMISING PRACTICES + NEEDS → TOOLS

Timeframe: 35 minutes

Material:

- Coloured name badges or name tags + coloured sticky dots
- 1 marker
- Audio-recorder
- Screen and beamer
- Supporting presentation slides
- Informed consent forms
- Participant list
- Pens

E.2 Session 2: RRI Working Definition

E.2.1 Session 2 overview: goals, format, duration, results

The RRI Tools project not only aspires to develop tools for responsible research and innovation, but to operate responsibly itself as well. One element of that aspiration is the iterative development of the working definition. Recurrently, we want to incorporate the ideas and concerns of local stakeholders across Europe to come to an increasingly better understanding of the concept of RRI.

Session 2 of the workshop aims to inform target users of the RRI concept and engage them in the future Community of Practice – NHCs have to set the nucleus in their regions for RRI communities of practices. The session lasts one hour and 35 minutes (breaks excluded) and consists of two dialogue activities following structured guidelines (Annex IV, Session 2) and a short follow-up e-mail survey (Annex VI) to complement results.

The methodology of this session is designed to fulfil the following objectives:

- Gather feedback and comments on the working definition of RRI for this project;
- Exchange practical experiences with RRI processes among participants.

Results of the session will be structured summaries of the group discussions, including photos and translations of the flip charts. The report from each NHC will follow the same structure through the reporting template provided (Annex VII). The analysis of the results will be used to optimize the working definition of RRI used in the project.

E.2.2 Session 2 guidelines

The following section is intended to serve as an explanation and instructions for the moderator. Annex IV (Session 2) provides the script with guidelines for use in real time during the workshop.

EXERCISE 0. ON-GOING ACTIVITY

Objectives:

- Collect any questions/issues not tackled during the workshop, to be documented later in the reporting template (Annex VII).

During plenary discussions and exercises some aspects might come up that could not immediately be tackled or taken into account in the on-going exercise. Therefore, an empty flip chart should be offered to collect these untackled aspects. The list shows participants that no aspect will be dropped or forgotten and that they will be documented in the reporting as well.

Timeframe: whole workshop

Material:

- Empty flip chart
- 1 marker

EXERCISE 1. THE RRI WORKING DEFINITION

Objectives:

- To disseminate the working definition of RRI and to gain feedback from the participants.

The current state of RRI and its definition is presented by explaining why RRI is necessary, what it is exactly and how we think it should be reached. Before discussing the working definition, the stakeholders will get a few moments to discuss the why of RRI and their possible roles in RRI (flip chart 1).

The participants are enabled to provide feedback on the RRI working definition by expressing and explaining their (first) ideas regarding the definition. The moderator will collect the ideas by writing them on yellow sticky notes (post-its) and place them on flip chart 2.

The exercise is closed by asking the participants if there are aspects outside the four clusters of process requirements (diversity & inclusion, openness & transparency, anticipation & reflection, responsiveness & adaptive change) they think are missing.

Timeframe: 75 minutes

Material:

- Flip chart 1 with stakeholders
- Flip chart 2 with four process requirements clusters
- Yellow sticky notes
- Markers
- Supporting presentation slides

EXERCISE 2. EXPERIENCES OF PARTICIPANTS

Objectives

- To exchange practical experiences with RRI processes among participants;
- To enhance the experienced connection to the RRI movement.

In two steps the personal experience of participants with processes that involved one or more of the four clusters of process requirement and outcomes are explored, shared and discussed. During the first 10 minutes of the exercise, participants will explore their experiences with their neighbour. In step two the most prominent experiences are shared and discussed with the whole group. The moderator writes the input down in keywords on pink sticky notes.

Timeframe: 20 minutes

Material:

- Flip chart from Exercise 1
- Pink sticky notes
- Markers
- Supporting presentation slides

BREAK

A coffee break is suggested between Sessions 2 and 3 (adapt time to your local needs).

E.3 Session 3: Compilation of Promising RRI Practices

E.3.1 Session 3 overview: goals, format, duration, results

The RRI Tools project aims to gather promising practices across Europe to develop a catalogue of good practice standards. The hubs are the primary source for these practices. The promising practices will be collected by the NHCs (and hub members, if applicable), as well as by the stakeholders participating in the workshop, as specified in [Deliverable 1.2](#). The stakeholders will bring a brief and simple description of a promising practice to the workshop. Session 3 aims to collect and discuss further these promising practices in light of the RRI working definition. A selected set of these practices will be analysed further by the NHCs after the workshop.

Session 3 consists of three interactive assessment and dialogue activities, during which opportunity is provided to obtain an overview of them and rank the most successful strategies that fulfil one or more process requirements. Session 3 will last one hour and 20 minutes (breaks excluded) and its results will be complemented with a short follow-up e-mail survey (Annex VI). The script that needs to be followed during the session can be found in Annex IV (Session 3).

The methodology of this session is designed to fulfil the following objectives:

- Collect a list of local, regional, national, and international best practices;
- Make a first, bottom-up classification of local, regional, national, and international promising practices;
- Insight into the potential role of promising practices in the RRI Tools project and beyond.

Results of the session will be structured summaries of the group discussions, including translations and photos of the flip charts, and translated filled in 'three-questions' answer sheets. The report from each NHC will follow the same structure through the reporting template provided (Annex VII). The analysis of the results will be used to optimize the working definition and to extract and formulate Good Practice Standards.

E.3.2 Session 3 guidelines

The following sections are intended to serve as explanations and instructions for the moderator. Annex IV (Session 3) provides the script with guidelines for use in real time during the workshop.

EXERCISE 3. STRONG AND WEAK POINTS OF PROMISING PRACTICES

Objectives

- To obtain an understanding of strong/weak points of the provided promising practices from the perspective of the participants.

The idea of promising RRI practices is briefly explained by the moderator. The explanation should follow the PowerPoint presentation, addressing that promising practices:

- can be concrete instruments, activities, programs or organisations that provide a successful strategy for one or more of the process requirements of RRI;
- are innovative and feasible approaches beyond the common practice;
- strive towards the RRI outcomes;
- have considerable and assessable positive effects;
- are transferable to other organizations, initiatives or contexts.

Following the explanation, every participant is asked to fill in individually part B of the promising practices question sheet (Annex III). This sheet addresses strong and weak points of the promising practice in terms of RRI. Part A of the question sheet should have been filled in by participants in preparation to the workshop (see Section B.3). After filling in part B of the sheet, the answers will be discussed in pairs. This discussion will lead to a list of four strong points and four weak points of promising RRI practices, which will be further discussed in small groups of four participants. The participants are asked to cluster the strong and weak points and provide the clusters with a title.

Timeframe: 50 minutes

Material:

- Sticky notes (green and pink)
- Markers
- 4 empty flip charts
- 20 copies the promising RRI practice question sheet part B (blank)
- 5 extra copies of the promising RRI practice question sheet part A (blank)
- Supporting presentation slides

EXERCISE 4. WHAT CHARACTERIZES PROMISING PRACTICES?

Objectives

- To obtain an understanding of the characteristics of a promising RRI practice from the perspective of the participants.

The clusters of the previous exercise will be discussed plenary during this exercise. Subgroups can explain the most often mentioned or most thought-provoking strong and weak points of promising RRI practices. After visualising the clusters plenary, participants are asked what they think characterizes a (promising) practice of RRI and what strategies make these aspects come into being.

Timeframe: 25 minutes

Material:

- Flip charts made during Exercise 3
- Blank flip chart
- Markers
- Supporting presentation slides

WRAP-UP

Objectives

- To close down Sessions 2 and 3 and offer space for additional comments, ideas, questions and suggestions.

Close down Sessions 2 and 3 and offer space for additional comments, ideas, questions and suggestions. Invite the participants to lunch.

Timeframe: 5 minutes

LUNCH BREAK

After lunch, an energizer may be done to enhance energy levels and to create a friendly and open atmosphere.

E.4 Session 4: Stakeholder Consultation

E.4.1 Session 4 overview: goals, format, duration, results

Session 4 of the workshop aims at assessing stakeholders' needs and constraints related to RRI. This session will last 3 hours (excluding breaks) and will take place in the afternoon, after Sessions 1 to 3 and preferably a lunch break. Timeframes can be extended according to requirements and availabilities of the participants, but they should not be reduced.

The session consists of three interactive assessment and dialogue activities along a structured guideline (Annex IV, Session 4), plus a complementary follow-up e-mail survey (Annex VI). The methodology of this session is designed to fulfil the following objectives:

- ***To assess the attitudes of stakeholders towards RRI and the extent to which they already perceive themselves as participating in the RRI process.*** The willingness of stakeholders to adapt their existing practices to RRI or adopt new ones is crucial to the success of the Toolkit. The session should find out reactions of participants in order to adapt the Toolkit to its target users, both in terms of the content and the way it is communicated to them.
- ***To identify the main needs of the RRI Toolkit's target users to increase their participation in the RRI process.*** These needs may take the form of concrete tools, partnerships that need to be forged, resources to be made available, training or others.
- ***To identify the constraints currently limiting the participation of stakeholders in the RRI process.*** These constraints might not necessarily be addressed directly by the Toolkit, but could rather be seen as boundaries within which the toolkit will need to function. They could include the way stakeholders typically work, ethical, legal, social and cultural aspects, issues of the way research and innovation is financed, etc.
- ***To gain an overview of these questions across a range of stakeholder groups and EU countries.*** In order to ensure the RRI Toolkit is best adapted to all potential users, it is essential to take into account a range of voices from across the target user groups, both in terms of the sector where the stakeholder works and their national background.
- ***To engage and mobilise participants.*** A secondary objective of the whole workshop is that by identifying, contacting, and consulting stakeholders who could also potentially be future users of the RRI Toolkit, we are making a first step in the direction of the mobilisation phase of the project. Furthermore, we are bringing different stakeholder groups to work together on these issues.

Results of the session will be structured summaries of the group discussions. The report from each hub will follow the same structure through the reporting template provided (Annex VII). The analysis of the results will be used by the project to feed the production of the RRI Toolkit.

E.4.2 Session 4 guidelines

The following sections are intended to serve as explanations and instructions for the moderator. Annex IV (Session 4) provides the script with guidelines for use in real time during the workshop.

EXERCISE 5. INTRODUCTION TO SESSION 4

Objectives

- Ensure participants understand the objectives of Session 4.
- Allow participants to get to know each other (only in case of new participants).

Participants should have previously attended Sessions 1 to 3, since Session 4 contents highly depend on the previous ones. Therefore, NHCs are strongly encouraged to keep the same participants for the whole workshop.

However, in some particular cases a few participants may change, as not all will be able to stay for a whole day. In that case, if new persons come only for Session 4, a short RRI Tools project introduction and a short summary of the morning workshop should be given to the newcomers before starting the afternoon workshop (use PowerPoint slides provided for the morning workshop, give examples of promising practices).

At the beginning of Session 4 new participants should also be introduced to the rest of the group (if not done before), as well as let them know about the empty flip chart (see E.2.2, Exercise 0).

Moderator then introduces Session 4 objectives and expected outcomes.

Timeframe: 20 minutes (or less if there are no newcomers)

- Introduction to Session 4 aims.
- Introduction round for participants (only if new participants present).
- Alternatively, use an 'energizer' to give some gas to the participants after lunch and to revive a friendly and open atmosphere.

Material:

- Tables (in circle)
- Chairs
- Name tags colour coded by stakeholder group for new participants (see E.1.2)
- RRI Tools overview supporting presentation slides (only for new participants)

EXERCISE 6. OBSTACLES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Objectives

- Participants think about opportunities and obstacles related to working more closely with the RRI process and collect them.

In this part we mix pairs of different stakeholder groups. This way they will exchange their experiences, but also produce opportunity and obstacle cards with the different stakeholders' perspectives. The exercise consists of two steps:

Firstly the participants identify opportunities and obstacles related to their daily work and exchange about them, writing these aspects on coloured cards (one colour for obstacles, one colour for opportunities). The discussion in pairs takes 20 minutes. Secondly participants come back to plenary and present their cards to the group briefly and give further explanations, if necessary. The moderator pins the cards in the appropriate column. Related aspects are grouped together. The moderator can write the title of each cluster on a post-it or card of the third colour. Other participants join in, one pair after the other, using the pop-corn method⁶, and relate to the already pinned cards. Repetitions and overlaps become visible this way and also if some aspects were mentioned by different stakeholders or just once. The plenary finally can see the whole picture and the moderator gives a summary of the different clustered topics.

Timeframe: 45 minutes (20 min + 25 min)

- Participants sit together in pairs (one group of three is possible). This activity could also be carried out as 'paired walks' (especially recommended after lunch).
- Participants write cards (obstacles in one colour, opportunities in other), initialising their stakeholder affiliation on the cards (see initials in E.1.2). They could either initial one or more groups, if applicable.
- Only one aspect per card, write as many cards as necessary.
- Come back to plenary and present the cards. Make sure the board for placing the notes is big enough to allow a clear view of the emerging conceptual map.
- Moderator clusters the cards in two columns, starting with the obstacles. Ask participants to help/clarification/agreement to keep them focused.

Material:

- Cards of three colours (obstacles, opportunities, titles of clusters)
- Flip chart markers
- 1 pin wall prepared with two columns
- Pins

⁶ Pop-corn method: collect one card and then ask: *does anybody have the same point? Or does anybody have a totally different point?* Continue until all the cards are collected.

Example of clustered opportunities and obstacles.

Oval card: cluster title; blue card: opportunity; orange card: obstacle.

BREAK

A coffee break is suggested between Exercises 6 and 7 (adapt time to your local needs).

EXERCISE 7. IDENTIFY ACTIONS AND SOLUTIONS

Objectives

- Work out lists of suggested actions/solutions per stakeholder group based on the formulated obstacles and opportunities.

In this exercise participants for the first time come together in homogeneous stakeholder groups. They discuss from the perspective of their group the list of obstacles and opportunities as put together in Exercise 6. To start with, they decide which of the identified clustered topics are the most relevant for them. Along these topics they discuss and formulate actions and/or solutions that reflect their needs. Moderator encourages participants to pick more than one topic.

Exercises 7 and 8 are the core elements of Session 4, which should provide a deeper understanding of the needs of the different stakeholder groups. The important and difficult task is to come up with needs and requirements, based on the formulated opportunities and obstacles. Therefore, in Exercise 7 participants are asked to formulate suggested actions/solutions for the identified topics. They have to be briefed carefully on how to transform aspects into these actions/solutions. General and open formulated solutions, such as “more money”, should be avoided. Actions/solutions should be formulated as concrete, grounded and practical as possible. Participants discuss in homogeneous stakeholder groups and prepare to present the outcomes in Exercise 8.

In case the groups move to different rooms, make sure they all have the list of opportunities and

obstacles to work with. For instance, during the previous break you can:

- take pictures of the clusters with tablets and provide them to the groups;
- or copy the clusters on new flip charts and give them to the groups.

Timeframe: 35 minutes

- Split into 5 stakeholder groups.
- Carry out formulated actions and/or solutions for the most relevant aspects.
- Formulate as precisely as possible.

Material:

- Pin wall with clustered opportunities and obstacles
- 5 flip chart papers (1 per group)
- 5 markers (1 per group)

EXERCISE 8. COMPILATION OF NEEDS FOR STAKEHOLDER ACTIONS AND SOLUTIONS

Objectives

- Overall view and discussion of needs per stakeholder group.

The stakeholder groups come back to the plenary and present their lists in 25 minutes (5 minutes per group). Plenary can comment, ask, or complement. After the presentation of the 5 groups, the plenary brainstorms on what is needed to make these actions and solutions work. The moderator guides the brainstorm and integrates the existing flip charts with new inputs coming from the plenary. If needed, use a new empty flip chart to write new needs as they arise from the plenary. Also, the moderator can use coloured cards to add the stakeholder group affiliation to the actions/solutions as they are discussed in the plenary. The aim is, at the end of the exercise, to come up with revised and finalised flip charts per stakeholder groups' needs (including suggestions for precise actions and needed tools).

In case the brainstorm does not have enough outcomes, allow participants to reflect within their stakeholder group and come back to the plenary brainstorm after 10-15 minutes.

Timeframe: 60 minutes (25 min + 35 min)

- Shortly, each group present their list of suggested actions/solutions (5 minutes per group = 25 minutes).
- Brainstorm on what is needed to achieve the actions/solutions (35 minutes).
- Specify the stakeholder group affiliation for each need that comes up. Create new flip charts if needed.

Material:

- Flip charts worked out per groups in Exercise 7.
- 1 marker
- Empty flip charts, if needed

CLOSURE, FEEDBACK, AND INTERPERSONAL EXCHANGE**Objectives**

- Summarize main results from Session 4.
- Tackle open issues (Exercise 0) not considered during the whole workshop.
- Explain what will happen with workshop outcomes.
- Invite to join the Community of Practice.
- Fill evaluation questionnaire (Annex V).
- Provide feedback round.
- Announce follow up e-mail survey (Annex VI) and close event.

Moderator closes and wraps up results of Session 4, also taking into consideration the open issues not tackled during the whole workshop but collected on flip chart (Exercise 0).

Moderator thanks the participants and explains what will happen with the workshop outcomes: the global analysis of the results from all the hubs will give us an overview of the differences across stakeholder groups and European countries and will allow us to develop the RRI Toolkit tailoring the tools to the needs expressed by each group. The workshop is also the starting point for building a Community of Practice across Europe and for future collaborations between the participants and the project.

Moving to the Consultation Workshop closure, the moderator will distribute the evaluation questionnaire for feedback (Annex V) and give a few minutes to fill it.

Then the moderator will freely adapt the most appropriate feedback round to give participants the chance to tell what they liked or did not like from the whole event (Sessions 1 to 4), what they take back home from the activity, if the knowledge/content/contacts will be useful for them in the future, and suggestions for improvement. It is suggested that you do not make a tour de table, since participants tend to disconnect. Instead, make use of the pop-corn method in combination with one of these examples for feedback rounds:

- “Eye-opener”: ask participants to distil one major impacting idea from the event;
- 3-word feedback: ask participants to summarize the workshop day in 3 words;
- Sandwich feedback: ask participants to say 1 negative aspect of the workshop day that is “sandwiched” between 2 positive aspects/lessons learnt.

Moderator finally announces a follow up short e-mail survey (Annex VI) to be sent immediately after the Consultation Workshop and closes the event.

Timeframe: 20 minutes

- Wrap up Session 4.
- Tackle open issues (Exercise 0).
- Explain outcomes analysis and invite to join the CoP.
- Distribute evaluation questionnaire (Annex V).
- Consultation Workshop feedback round.
- Announce follow up e-mail survey and closure.

Material:

- Open issues flip chart (Exercise 0)
- 20 copies of the evaluation questionnaire (Annex V)
- 20 pens

EVALUATION

F. Evaluation

In order to complement the results of the Consultation Workshop, NHCs should forward a short e-mail survey (Annex VI) to the workshop participants and to a wider list of 5-20 stakeholder contacts (preferably those who were invited but could not attend the workshop, but also further contacts) and ask them to answer until a certain deadline within two weeks.

NHCs will compile answers from both the questionnaire (Annex V) and the e-mail survey (Annex VI), translate them to English, and upload them anonymized to a folder specifically created for this purpose in the RRI Tools Dropbox account:

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/31okaxhxikgeutx/AAClhxslgVoia26fHeG4WTMOa>

Stakeholder affiliation information will be given, and also if the response of the e-mail survey comes from a workshop participant or not. Answers from individuals who did not attend the workshop will be analysed and weighted differently than the outcomes from the workshop attendees, to take into account the fact that the respondents have not engaged as fully as the workshop participants in the definition of RRI or the group dynamics of the event.

REPORTING

G. Reporting

NHCs, as hosts, also have to document and present the workshop results in a structured way, and thus a reporting template is provided (Annex VII). However, most of the outcomes will be produced by the workshop participants themselves. This minimises the work of NHCs in reporting and aims to ensure that as few details as possible are lost. Photos of all flip charts created by the participants and additional information (based on assistant's notes and general observations, feedback notes, audio recordings, etc.), given according to the reporting template, will provide a whole picture of the event. The workshops will finally come up with conclusions and ranked issues that will also need to be incorporated in the template.

The workshops are organised in local languages, but the report is written by each NHC in English. Photos of texts from the workshop will need to be captioned by the NHCs in English. These and other artefacts, such as tables and ranked lists, have to be documented in English by the NHCs.

NHCs are asked to report all data regarding the Consultation Workshop to a folder specifically created for this purpose in the RRI Tools Dropbox account:

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/31okaxhxikgeutx/AAClhxslgVoia26fHeG4WTMOa>

Each NHC will have to upload to its corresponding Hub subfolder the following materials:

- Reporting template (Annex VII);
- Filled in Question Sheets (parts A and B, translated into English) for each promising RRI practice that has been put forward by the participants or the NHCs (see section E.3.2 Session 3 guidelines and [Deliverable 1.2](#));
- Individual files for pictures (optional).

After the workshop and the upload of the reporting materials, Athena Institute will contact NHCs to discuss which promising practices will be used for the Online Questionnaire (see Deliverable 1.2).

ANNEXES

Annex I

Stakeholders mapping tables

Annex I. Stakeholder mapping tables

For a more comprehensive stakeholder mapping see [D2.1 Guidelines for the implementation of the stakeholder consultation in relation to RRI](#).

Civil Society Organisation Stakeholders Mapping

SPHERE OF COMPETENCE	TYPE	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
Needs of Specific Groups			
Local	<i>Faith based organisations</i>	Advisory board	Volunteers
	<i>Community-based organisations</i> Environment, Health, Ethics/Gender, Education, Policy	Board members, general manager	Project manager
	<i>Social movements</i> Environment, Health, Ethics/Gender, Education, Policy	Organizing committee	Project manager, volunteers
Regional	<i>Foundations</i> Environment, Health, Education	Head of scientific content, Programme manager	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Faith-based organisations</i>	Head of programmes	Head of external relations
	<i>Trade unions</i> Policy	Head of scientific content, Programme manager	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
National	<i>Community-based organisations</i> Environment, Health, Ethics/Gender, Education, Policy	Head of scientific content, Programme manager	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Foundations</i> Environment, Health, Education	Head of scientific content, Programme manager	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Faith based organisations</i>	Head of programmes	Head of external relations
Transnational	<i>Trade unions</i> Policy	Head of scientific content	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Foundations</i> Environment, Health, Education	Head of scientific content, Programme manager	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Faith based organisations</i>	Head of programmes	Head of external relations

SPHERE OF COMPETENCE	TYPE	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
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General Societal Issues

Local	<i>NGO / Associations</i> Environment, Health	Head of scientific content or Head of Education	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Non-for-Profit / Charity</i> Environment, Health,	Head of scientific content	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
Regional	<i>NGO / Associations</i> Environment, Health	Head of scientific content	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Non-for-Profit / Charity</i> Environment, Health	Head of scientific content	Director, project managers, head of external relations...

Civil Society Organisation Stakeholders Mapping

SPHERE OF COMPETENCE	TYPE	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
National	<i>NGO / Associations</i> Environment, Health, Ethics/Gender, Education, Policy	Head of scientific content	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Non-for-Profit / Charity</i> Environment, Health, Ethics/Gender, Education, Policy	Head of scientific content	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Independent research institutes</i> Environment, Health, Ethics/Gender, Education, Policy	Head of scientific content, Programm manager	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	Foundations Environment, Health, Ethics/Gender, Education, Policy	Head of programmes	Head of external relations
	<i>Trade Unions</i> Environment, Health, Ethics/Gender, Policy	Head of scientific content, Programme manager	Director, project managers, head of external relations...
	<i>Faith based organisations</i>	Head of programmes	Head of external relations

Education community Stakeholders Mapping

ORGANISATION TYPE	ORGANISATION/BODY	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
Formal Education			
Ministry of Education	Ministry of Education	Head of curriculum development and STEM education	n/a
Ministry of Education	National Agency in charge of STEM/innovation/ICT in education	Head of curriculum development and STEM education	n/a
Ministry of Education	National Board of Education	Member of national board of education	n/a
Regional/Community authorities	Responsible for curriculum development and STEM education	n/a	n/a
Local authorities /Municipalities	Authority in charge of school management	n/a	n/a
STEM Teacher associations	Director of teacher association	n/a	n/a
Schools	Pre and Primary School	Headmaster	Teacher
	Secondary school	Headmaster and career counsellors	Teacher
Universities			
Training institutions	Head of STEM Education		
Research institutes	Head of STEM education		
Industries	CSR – Department in charge of education programmes		
International European organisations	European Schoolnet		
Informal Education			
Museum	Natural History , Science, Art, Maritime, Children,Pop up	Head of scientific content, head of education	Director, Project managers, head of external relations
Science centre, Zoo, Aquarium, Botanical Garden		Head of scientific content, head of education	Director, roject managers, head of external relations
Library		Head of programmes	Director, Project managers

Education community Stakeholders Mapping

ORGANISATION TYPE	ORGANISATION/BODY	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
Community organisations	Youth organisations, Afterschool organizations	President	Programme Manager
	Community-based research centre	Community leader	Programme Manager
Science shop		Coordinator	Programme Manager
Science Festival		Head of programmes	Director
Science Cafe		Programme Manager	
Children's university		Head of programme	Dean

Industry and business Stakeholders Mapping

SECTOR	TYPE OF INSTITUTION	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Mining and Quarrying	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Manufacturing	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Electricity, Gas, Steam and Air Conditioning Supply	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO

Industry and business Stakeholders Mapping

SECTOR	TYPE OF INSTITUTION	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Water supply, Sewerage, Waste management and Remediation Activities	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Construction	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Transportation and Storage	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Accommodation and Food Service Activities	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Information and Communication	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO

Industry and business Stakeholders Mapping

SECTOR	TYPE OF INSTITUTION	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
Financial and Insurance Activities	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Real Estate Activities	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	
Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Administrative and Support Service Activities	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Human Health and Social Work Activities	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO

Industry and business Stakeholders Mapping

SECTOR	TYPE OF INSTITUTION	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
Arts, Entertainment and Recreation	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO
Other Service Activities	Other innovation sources (in-house)	Heads of department	CEO, COO, CTO
	Outsourced innovation	CEO, CTO, Head of Procurement	COO
	Dedicated department	Head of R&D	CEO

Policymakers Stakeholders Mapping

TYPE	ROLE	BODY OR EXAMPLE	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
European				
Government	Executive	European Commission	Chief Scientific Officer and Team	President
	Funder	EC DG (Research / Enterprise)	Science With and For Society Team	Commissioner
	Legislative	European Parliament	ITRE Committee and Individual MEPs	Committee Chair / Negotiation Rapporteur
Agency	Funder	European Research Council	Council	President
	Funder / enabler	European Space Agency	Outreach and Comms Team	Division Directors
	Facility	CERN / ESO	Outreach and Comms Team	Director
National				
Government	Executive	Cabinet of Ministers	Government Chief Scientific Advisor	Prime Minister / Ministers
		Departments	Departmental Chief Scientific Advisor plus Science Team	Ministers

Policymakers Stakeholders Mapping

TYPE	ROLE	BODY OR EXAMPLE	PRIMARY TARGET USER	SECONDARY TARGET USER
	Legislative	Parliament / Assembly	Individual Members of Committees	Committee Secretariat
Agency	Funder	Research Council	Science and Society / Comms Teams	Chief Executive / Director
	Regulatory	Various regulatory bodies	Head of policy	Chief Executive

Regional

Government	Executive / regulatory/ funder	Regional government bodies/ Devolved Assemblies	Science and Technology Groups / Committees plus Chief Scientific Advisor	Regional science ministers
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Local / Municipal

Government	Executive / regulatory	Local and municipal government bodies	Local council committee chairs and members	Local economic development officers
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Researchers Stakeholders Mapping

TYPE	ROLE	BODY OR EXAMPLE	PRIMARY TARGET USER AND SECONDARY TARGET USER
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European

Intergovernmental org.	Res. infrastructure/ res. Performing	CERN, EMBL, ESA	Depends on RRI component selected and the appropriate contact points within the relevant stakeholder
Public company	Res. infrastructure/res. performing	European Spallation Source (ESS)	
Association of European labs	Res. infrastructure/res. performing	Association of European level research infrastructure facilities (ERF-AISBL)	
Association	University Associations	Coimbra Group, LERU, EUA	
Federation of academies	Learned societies and/or research performing organizations	ALLEA	

Researchers Stakeholders Mapping

TYPE	ROLE	BODY OR EXAMPLE	PRIMARY TARGET USER AND SECONDARY TARGET USER
Scientific organizations & learned societies	Not-for-profit inter-disciplinary organizations supporting research and education	EuroScience	
Scientific organizations & learned societies	Not-for-profit disciplinary organizations supporting research and education	Fed. of Eur. Bioch. Societies (FEBS), Eur. Physical Soc. (EPS)	
Research Council	Funding agency	European Research Council (ERC)	
European institution	Eur. Institution; funding body	European Commission	
Association	Association of Eur. Res. Funding Org. & Res. Perf. Org.	Science Europe	
Foundation	Research coordination and support organization	European Science Foundation (ESF)	
National			
Research facilities	Res. infrastructure/res. Performing	Elettra (IT), Synchrotron Soleil (FR)	Depends on RRI component selected and the appropriate contact points within the relevant stakeholder
Public research org.	Research performing	CNRS (FR), CSIC (SP), CNR (IT)	
Independent non-profit org.	Research performing	Max-Planck Society and Fraunhofer Gez. (DE)	
Public university	Education & research	Cambridge	
Academies	Learned societies	Académie des Sciences (FR)	
Academies	Research performing organizations	Hungarian Academy of Sciences	

Researchers Stakeholders Mapping

TYPE	ROLE	BODY OR EXAMPLE	PRIMARY TARGET USER AND SECONDARY TARGET USER
Scientific organizations & learned societies	Not-for-profit organizations supporting research and education	Royal Society of Chemistry (UK);	
Foundations	Funding organizations	Welcome Trust, Bosch Foundation	Depends on RRI component selected and the appropriate contact points within the relevant stakeholder
Funding agencies	Research funding organizations	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)	
Individuals			
Researchers	Research and/or teaching	Need to identify individuals from various countries, career stages and disciplines.	Depends on RRI component selected and the appropriate contact points within the relevant stakeholder

Annex II

Invitation Letter Template

Annex II. Invitation letter template

This invitation, translated by NHCs to their local language, should be sent according to the instructions of section B.3, after direct contact with potential candidates to attend the workshop. Accompanying material should include a short summary of the project, as well as basic dissemination material (web and social media links, digital leaflet – see C.1). Additionally, they should make clear that the workshop is only the initial point in building a wide Community of Practice, and that participating in it will allow attendees to become the nucleus of this CoP in their area of influence.

[RRI Tools logo]

[Your institution logo]

[City, date]

Dear [title, surname]

[Your institution] is honoured to invite you to be part of the European project RRI Tools, funded by the European Commission's 7th Framework Programme. We are coordinating in [country] the creation of a [working group] to foster Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) at European level.

A first meeting will be held in [place/venue] on [date], from [hour] to [hour], with leading representatives from research, education, policy, civil society organisations, industry and business. Our purpose is to share thoughts on what is RRI and to identify promising practices, constraints and needs from all the stakeholder groups involved in this emerging field for the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme.

Your experience in [field (e.g., policy making, higher education)] will be a key contribution for the meeting and further on the project, where you will have the opportunity to convey the concerns and expectations of your field of expertise.

We sincerely hope that you will be able to accept this invitation. The project will cover your travel and accommodation expenses and provide you with more information before the event.

Would you kindly confirm your participation by [date], to [name], at [e-mail].

In case you will not be able to join us, we would be grateful if you could suggest any colleague who might be interested in attending the meeting.

Yours sincerely,

[Signature]

[(Title) Name Surname]

[Institution, Department]

[E-mail]

[Telephone]

[Address]

Annex III

Information Package

Annex III. Information package

This information package consists of four sections: (1) the RRI information sheet, (2) the examples of promising RRI practices, (3) the promising RRI practice question sheet, and (4) the informed consent. Follow instructions provided in section B.4 for using this package.

1. RRI Information Sheet

What is responsible research and innovation?

Research and innovation constantly change our world. From the Internet and mobile phones, to climate change and new cancer treatments, science and technology have the potential to transform our lives. These developments also create new risks and new ethical dilemmas. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) seeks to bring these issues into the open, anticipate the consequences and directions of research and innovation, and involve society in discussing how science and technology can help create the kind of world and future we want.

Why responsible research and innovation?

Increasingly powerful science and technology have granted humans unprecedented scope to intervene in our surroundings, from altering ecosystems and the Earth's climate at the global scale to manipulating the minute building blocks of matter and life itself. In addition, as a society we face great challenges – from healthy ageing to sustainability, from global health to resource security. Research and innovation have the power to tackle these challenges, but their success is not guaranteed.

Research and innovation will always be at least partly unpredictable, but this does not excuse irresponsibility. Understanding and taking responsibility for these developments goes well beyond just science and scientists. Such developments profoundly affect all our lives. The direction and purpose of research and innovation, the distribution of its outcomes (both positive and negative), the uses of new technologies, and maintaining a focus on solving pressing problems are matters that we, as a society, need to discuss and choose together.

What should responsible research and innovation look like?

RRI is not one thing. It will vary across institutions, cultures and areas of science and technology. However, it will have one key, central feature: it will put the needs of ordinary citizens at its centre. Companies will still need to make profits in a market economy, but RRI will re-orientate research from “can this make money?” to “how can this fulfil the needs of society within the market?”.

What about ‘fundamental’ research?

Fundamental research is not aimed at meeting the immediate, material needs of society. The deep insights into the world in which we live –from sub-atomic to universal scales, from the micro-biotic to the global environment– are a vital part of human culture. RRI applies to all stages and aspects of research, including fundamental research. It demands that the knowledge gained be open and accessible to all, and that its starting point be engagement with as many of the world's citizens who want to participate in creating that new knowledge as possible.

Whose needs, whose challenges?

How, then, to uncover the needs of our fellow citizens? Over the last few decades, we have seen many experiments that foster involvement of the public in discussions and policy decisions regarding science, collaboration between scientists, ethicists and social scientists, open source and user-driven innovation, citizen science and more besides. We should encourage such experiments, join them up and encourage the institutions that fund, regulate and govern science and innovation to respond to them.

RRI means experimenting further and improving upon existing practice. It means paying close attention to current developments, be they positive efforts by scientists to take responsibility for emerging technologies, or institutional and cultural barriers that are stopping progress. RRI also encompasses research ethics, gender and other forms of inclusion, open access to scientific data and publications, and scientific education. Scientists and innovators should be encouraged to take responsibility for the futures they help shape. But the responsibility is not individual, nor is it theirs alone. The challenge is to find collective ways to take care of the future.

2. Examples of promising RRI practices

During the coming months, the RRI Tools project will look at existing practices that may have RRI potential, as we can learn from ‘real world’ experiences with RRI. These promising practices of responsible research and innovation should exert a variety of features brought to light in the RRI information sheet.

RRI is about anticipating how our decisions regarding research and innovation might shape the future and about reflecting on our actions, while being open and transparent about these decisions and actions. It should not merely recognize the needs and wishes of stakeholders, but also shape directions of research and innovation in response to a diverse set of perspectives and to changing circumstances. RRI aims to create a society in which responsibility for our future is shared by all people and institutions involved and in which research and innovation practices strive towards ethically acceptable, sustainable and socially desirable outcomes.

The RRI Tools project aims to collect a variety of promising practices: they can be instruments, projects, programmes, or organisations. For each type of RRI practice we provide you with an example from the Netherlands. We kindly ask you to come up with one promising RRI practice in the region you live or work and note down some basic information about that practice on the attached question sheet in preparation to the workshop.

Example of instrument: Techno-moral vignettes (Rathenau Institute)

To envision possible futures for synthetic biology Rathenau Institute (Netherlands) wrote a number of techno-moral ‘vignettes’; short stories describing possible futures of technology in our society and lives. Techno-moral vignettes are not speculative predictions of the future, but describe possible future events based on current developments in and knowledge of the research fields relating to the technology. They are called techno-moral because they explore both the different fields of application of the technology and the moral concerns raised by it. The vignettes can be seen as a promising practice of RRI as they try to open up the discussion about how technology can affect our world, ideas, needs, values and ideals. The vignettes invite everybody to think about if and how innovations can improve our world, aiming not only to include the general public, but scientists and politicians as well. This instrument could be used for a broad range of innovations and to seek a better understanding of how these innovations could change the way we live and how they may contribute to a better world.

Example of project: ‘Seeking Sociable Swine’ (Wageningen University, VU Amsterdam, and the Institute for Pig Genetics)

In the Netherlands animal welfare in animal production has acquired a permanent place on the political, scientific and private agenda. Within the research project ‘Seeking Sociable Swine’, researchers from different disciplines worked together to create a shared solution for animal welfare improvement in pig production. From the start of the project stakeholders were involved via a multi-stakeholder dialogue, facilitating the process of reflecting on one’s own and the total diversity of perspectives at stake. The aims of the project were dual: while generating scientific knowledge (animal genetics research), the research realises a problem-oriented, learning intervention and functions to contribute to sustainable development.

Example of programme: Responsible Innovation (NWO, ‘Maatschappelijk verantwoord innoveren’)

The Dutch research funding program NWO/MVI (Responsible innovation) is directed at technological

developments that presumably have large (both positive and negative) impacts on individuals and societies. These developments encompass on the one hand new emerging technologies, such as nanotechnology and ICT, and on the other hand technological systems in transition, such as agriculture and health. The program contributes to socially responsible innovation by broadening and deepening the study of ethical and societal aspects of technological trajectories in both national and international contexts. Interdisciplinary collaboration and a pro-active design perspective aim to ensure that the understanding of ethical and societal aspects is actively incorporated into the innovation trajectories.

Example of organisation: The Netherlands Lung Foundation

The Netherlands Lung Foundation (NLF) is considered one of the pioneers of patient involvement in health research in the Netherlands. It consists of both a research-funding agency and a patient organisation, which hold a strong relationship. The NLF might be called an example of an RRI organisation, as they try to incorporate stakeholder involvement as a 'normal practice' in their organisation. Because of the double role of the NLF, they hold an extensive network including researchers, health professionals, and patients. Acknowledging the value of all perspectives for addressing lung disease related issues, NLF includes them in agenda setting activities. Furthermore, NLF acquired a leading role among health funding agencies in the Netherlands by developing other forms of patient involvement: it changed its guidelines for proposal writing (e.g., submitting a 'lay summary' so that patients can judge the proposals), it communicates patient involvement for the research community (e.g., by presenting at scientific conferences and via publications), it participates in various international projects where patient involvement plays a role, and it established a pool of about twenty patients that received a two-day training course on patient involvement to prepare them to engage in research and gain insight into how researchers work and think. All these initiatives lead to better informed and more needs-oriented research and a stronger connection between the patient organisation and the research section.

3. Promising RRI practice question sheet ⁷

Part A

After reading the information sheet on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), can you think of an existing practice that might be an example of RRI? Could you please note down some information about that practice and bring it to the workshop?

Name / Title:

Organisation(s) involved:

Website of practice:

Contact person:

Aims to contribute to:

- Health, demographic change and wellbeing;
- Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research and the bio-economy;
- Secure, clean and efficient energy;
- Smart, green and integrated transport;
- Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials;
- Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative and reflective societies;
- Secure societies – protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens.

**General description:
(goals, activities, etc.)**

What makes this practice an example of RRI?

⁷ Note that Annex III contains both part A and B of the promising practice question sheet. Make sure you only send part A of this question sheet, since part B (which needs more time than part A) is only for being filled by participants during the workshop

Part B

Additional questions about the promising practice that relate to the RRI working definition. This part is filled in by the national Hub coordinators to collect promising practices and by stakeholders during the workshop.

Which RRI policy agenda(s) is or are addressed by the practice?

(more answers possible):

- Public engagement
- Ethics
- Science education
- Open access
- Gender
- Governance
- Other, namely....

What are the *strong* points of the practice in terms of process requirements?

What are the weak points of the practice in terms of process requirements?

To what extent are the RRI outcomes explicitly addressed/reached in the course of the practice?

- Engaged publics
- Responsible actors
- Responsible institutions
- Ethically acceptable outcomes
- Sustainable outcomes
- Socially desirable outcomes
- Solutions to societal challenges, namely...

Please explain

4. Informed consent

RRI Tools – A project to foster responsible research and innovation for society, with society

European Commission 7th Framework Project (FP7)

(Coordination and Support Action – Grant Agreement No. 612393)

Declaration of Consent

Name of participant:

Name of contact *[Insert local host here before printing]*

Project aims

RRI Tools is a 3-year FP7 project that seeks to develop adequate methods and tools to promote RRI and to make it applicable and verifiable, building a wide Community of Practice to assure the use, evolution and enrichment of the concept and the tools. The RRI Tools Consortium includes 26 institutions, covering 30 countries of the European Research Area through 19 Hubs.

In its first year RRI Tools is conducting stakeholder consultation activities in the 30 countries involved. Participatory Consultation Workshops are part of these activities, whose results will be analysed to update and finalize the common definition of RRI, collect promising RRI practices and tail the tools to the stakeholder needs.

Participation in the workshop

Participation in this workshop should take about 8 hours. Risks for participation should be negligible, but it can happen that you share sensitive opinions or confidential information inadvertently. Participation in the workshop is always voluntary: you may choose not to respond any question or discuss a particular topic, and you can leave the debate at your will.

Storage of personal data

During the course of the project, personal data will be collected by means of observation, interviews and group discussions. This data will be used to develop and to evaluate stakeholders' needs in the context of RRI, and requirements on RRI communication and training in particular.

Personal data will be used only within the framework of the RRI Tools project, and will not be made accessible for any third party. It will not be stored after the end of the project.

Personal data do not contain the names or addresses of participants and will be edited for full anonymity before being processed (e.g., in project reports).

Nature of data from group workshops

The organizers commit to maintain full confidentiality of data resulting from the workshop. Beware though that this will be a group discussion. The organization will ask participants to respect confidentiality, but this cannot be guaranteed.

Audiovisual material

Videos and photographs taken during the course of the project may contain the pictures of participants. RRI Tools may use these materials in public forums, conferences or on websites to inform about the project. Each participant allows RRI Tools to use the said materials.

Each participant may demand removal of photographs or videos from websites and public forums by simple request. Subject to technical feasibility, RRI Tools agrees to remove the requested items without delay.

Instructions and advice

An identified contact person (National Hub Coordinator) will be available for project-related instructions and advice. Each participant may gladly discuss questions and problems with this person at any time.

Code of Conduct

Participation in RRI Tools is meant to be as agreeable and pleasant as possible for all those involved. Therefore, all participants agree to respect the following rules:

- Racism and discrimination: racist comments, discrimination on the basis of sex, age, or disability, publication of racist or sexist pictures and insulting persons are strictly banned.
- RRI Tools may not be abused for political, religious or advertising purposes.
- Infringements of copyright laws are not permitted.
- All participants' conduct towards other users should always be appropriate and never offensive or depreciating.
- All participants will abstain from taking pictures or recording the workshop.

Consent

After having stated these general conditions and rules, we are looking forward to a good cooperation and positive project results. We would like to thank you in advance for your participation in the project RRI Tools.

The undersigned declare that they understand and consent to the conditions and rules of RRI Tools. Both parties receive a copy of this declaration of consent.

I hereby release RRI Tools and any of its associated or affiliated institutions, their directors, officers, agents, employees and customers from all claims of every kind on account of such use.

Participant's signature:

Location, day/month/year

Contact's signature:

Location, day/month/year

Annex IV

Session Scripts with Guidelines

Annex IV. Session scripts with guidelines

This Annex IV presents you with the extended version of the workshop script. This extended version provides you with the script to run the full workshop and it also mentions several important aspects and information. The script is to be studied in detail. It tells you when to say what, and every other action on your behalf necessary to properly moderate the event.

The script is in English. For matters of convenience, translate the script into your own language yourself. In the following text the bullet points refer to the text you should say to the participants. The rest is explanation for you.

For real-time use during the workshop it is recommended to have a printed copy of this Annex IV and the Checklist for organising the workshop (Annex VIII).

Session 1: Welcome and introduction

Timeframe: 35 minutes

- Registration and tracking: - (previous to the beginning of the workshop)
- Introduction, practicalities, participants and rules: 20 minutes
- Project introduction: 10 minutes
- Workshop overview: 5 minutes

Objectives

- Give welcome and practical information.
- Registration process.
- Allow participants to get to know each other.
- Provide an introduction of the RRI Tools project.
- Ensure participants understand the structure and objectives of the workshop.
- Create a climate of open exchange.

Registration

When participants enter the room welcome them, show them where can they leave their coats and luggage and, if possible, offer them something to drink. Try to create an open and friendly environment since the beginning of the workshop day.

Ask them to sign the participant list that you have printed beforehand. Ask them to sign the informed consent forms that you have sent them beforehand. Make sure you collect all the informed consent forms signed.

Stakeholder tracking in different colours

In Session 4 participants will be asked to work in homogeneous stakeholder groups. To better identify these groups prepare name tags (or badges) and stick a coloured sticky dot on them that identifies the stakeholder group affiliation of each participant. Let participants to define themselves. This let participants the opportunity to act as representatives of several stakeholder groups based on their experience, if appropriate.

An example of colour coding could be (not necessary to follow this code):

Stakeholder group	Initials	Colour
Civil Society Organisations	CSO	yellow
Education Community	EDU	orange
Industry and Business	IND	red
Policymakers	POL	green
Researchers and Innovators	RES	blue

WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION

Moderator

Before participants enter put up the first slide of the PowerPoint presentation on the projector.

When it is time to start, sit down to introduce yourself.

- Welcome to this Consultation Workshop, I am happy that all of you are here. I welcome you on behalf of the RRI Tools project, a European project that aims to establish a toolkit for stakeholders involved in research and innovation to put RRI into practice.
- My name is *<your name>* and I am the moderator for this workshop. I am working for (or linked to) *<name of your organisation>*.
- My role is to maintain the focus and to guide and stimulate the discussion.
- Besides me sits *<name assistant>*. She/he will take notes during the discussion, keep time and will assist me in other things during this workshop.

Practicalities

- Is it okay to audio-record the workshop and use the data? Everything will be anonymized. Please let me know if you have questions.

Turn on audio recorder.

Tell participants where they can find the restroom.

Participants

Ask the participants to introduce themselves briefly by mentioning:

- their name and affiliation
- their relation to research and innovation

Keep the introductory round short. Use some kind of icebreaker to get people involved and establish a safe and non-threatening environment. On the internet you can find many examples of icebreakers aimed at creating a positive atmosphere and getting to know each other.

House rules

- Please turn off and put away phones, laptops, tablets, etc.
- It is important that we all listen to others, reflect on what is said and respect alternative points of view. All inputs are equally valued.
- We encourage you to take notes as people talk, so no important ideas are left behind.
- Be open to new ideas and concepts. Discussions and criticisms must focus on issues, not on people.
- Do not just raise problems: think about solutions!
- Together we are responsible on what is written on flip charts, which in turn will inform the written report of the workshop.
- Please adhere to timings and to our instructions, and... have fun!

Introduction to the project

Use the next slide in the PowerPoint presentation to explain about the RRI Tools project (comments for the moderator provided in the presentation)

Overview of the Consultation Workshop

Use the next two slides in the PowerPoint presentation to explain the overall structure, goals and outcomes of the Consultation Workshop (comments for the moderator provided in the presentation).

Session 2: RRI working definition

EXERCISE 0. ON-GOING ACTIVITY

Timeframe: 1 minute (whole workshop)

Introduce the empty flipchart before the starting:

Moderator (or assistant) collects any questions/issues not tackled during the exercises, to be documented later in the reporting template and be answered (if possible) during later sessions or at the end of the workshop. Prepare an empty flipchart pinned on a wall to serve this purpose.

During plenary discussions and exercises some aspects might come up that could not immediately be tackled or taken into account in the on-going exercise. We will use this flipchart to collect them. We will tackle open issues at the end of the day. All the aspects will be documented and taken into account during the analysis of the workshop outcomes.

EXERCISE 1. THE RRI WORKING DEFINITION

Timeframe: 75 minutes

- Presentation: 20 minutes
- Small discussions: 25 minutes
- Exercise 1: 30 minutes

Objectives:

- To disseminate the working definition of RRI and to gain feedback from the participants

Use the next slide of the PowerPoint presentation to explain the participants about the working definition of RRI that has been produced in the first half year of the project.

Explain how the working definition was produced:

- We have gathered and processed many different accounts of Responsible Research and Innovation available in the scientific literature and in policy documents. Based on this literature, we have developed ideas for a dynamic working definition. We expect the definition to change as we learn more about RRI in the course of the project. That is why we want to hear your ideas about the concept and feedback on our definition.

Explain what RRI is about in six steps using the PowerPoint presentation:

- Let me first explain to you how we view the concept of RRI.

Use the following texts as guidelines for your presentation:

- 1. WHY RRI:

As a society, we face Grand Societal challenges that are complex and uncertain - from

healthy ageing to sustainability, from global health to resource security. Research and innovation have the power to tackle these challenges, but their success is not guaranteed. Many innovations fail, have unexpected (negative) consequences and are controversial. Furthermore, some needs of society are not met (e.g., neglected diseases or neglected groups). Responsible research and innovation seeks to bring these issues into the open.

Take **10 minutes** to let the participants discuss the WHY of RRI together to validate the reasons for RRI. Write down interesting notions on a blank flip chart and ask in-depth questions if needed.

- 2. WHAT:

Aiming for RRI does not mean that individual people or organisations are irresponsible now. It means experimenting further and improving upon existing practice. It means paying close attention to current developments, be they positive efforts by scientists to take responsibility for emerging technologies, or institutional and cultural barriers that are stopping progress.

RRI is about a shared responsibility amongst a variety of stakeholders to establish an acceptable and desirable future. It is about anticipating the consequences and directions of research and innovation and involving society in discussing how science and technology can help create the kind of world and future we want. It demands that the knowledge gained by R&I is open and accessible to all, engaging everyone that wants to participate in creating new one.

- 3. WHEN:

RRI is an on-going process from start to finish. Although some aspects of RRI might be more pressing during specific stages of the research or innovation process, RRI should be incorporated during the whole process and in the people acting within that process. By this, we do not refer to every moment of the day but to every phase of the research or innovation process.

- 4. WHO:

The responsibility for taking care of the future is not individual, nor is it only that of researchers and innovators; R&I affect all our lives and we need to share responsibility. As a society we need to discuss the direction and purpose of research and innovation, the distribution of its outcomes (both positive and negative), the uses of new technologies, maintain a focus on solving pressing problems, and make decisions together. Within our society the project identified five stakeholder groups particularly involved in research and innovation: scientists, policymakers, the industry, CSOs, and educators. Today you represent these stakeholders of the R&I process and we invited you to share your thoughts on RRI with us.

Again, let the participants discuss the WHEN and WHO of RRI in **15 minutes**. Ask them:

- What do you think can or should be your role as a stakeholder group?

Ask in-depth questions if necessary and write their ideas down on prepared flip chart 1 as is shown in Figure AIV.1.

Scientists	Educators	Policy-makers	Industry	CSOs

Figure AIV.1. Prepared flip chart 1.

Here are some possible answers, so you know what to expect:

CSOs	Consult followers for their needs.
Educators	Raise awareness among young and new publics.
Industry	Broaden prototype testing to societal context.
Policymakers	Agenda setting, creating new funding opportunities.
Researchers	Involve users as co-researchers.

After the discussion, explain the details of the working definition we propose:

- 5. WHAT EXACTLY:

Responsible research and innovation is a dynamic, iterative process by which all stakeholders involved in the research and innovation practice become mutually responsive and share the responsibility regarding the RRI outcomes and processes. We identified three clusters of outcomes:

a. Learning outcomes: mutual learning across stakeholders and institutions.

- Engaged publics: Citizens empowered with skills to engage in RRI process effectively.
- Responsible actors: Actors think and act according to principles of RRI.
- Responsible institutions: RRI process institutionalized in academia and other relevant organizations.

b. R&I outcomes: products of R&I should be

- Ethically acceptable: specified (shared) values and norms for R&I process and products.
- Societally desirable: planet (environmental protection), people (social equity and cohesion), profit (economic prosperity).

- Sustainable: process and products responsive to socially desirable technology paths and future visions.
- c. Contributing to solutions for Grand Challenges.
- 6. HOW:

We should establish an on-going process of inquiry and deliberation in which a wide range of stakeholders and citizens are involved. This process should fulfil a set of requirements that we call the process requirements of RRI. There are eight and we distributed them in four clusters:

a. Inclusion and diversity

 - Wide range of stakeholders.
 - Inclusive practices lead to diverse practices.
 - Diverse practices lead to inclusive practices.

b. Openness and transparency

 - Openness should lead to increased transparency and better science.
 - Openness and transparency are conditions for accountability, liability and responsibility.
 - Level of openness depends on context.
 - Information needs to be tailored to stakeholder needs.

c. Anticipation and reflection

 - Anticipation and reflection complement each other.
 - Understanding how present dynamics of science and technology shape the future.
 - First-order, second-order and third-order learning.

d. Responsiveness and adaptive change

 - Responsiveness means responding to emerging knowledge, perspectives, views and norms.
 - Responsiveness is a condition for adaptive change.
 - Adaptive change is about shaping directions in response to stakeholder values and changing circumstances (both ad hoc and continuously).

Move on to collect the responses and feedback of the participants (**30 minutes**).

- What do you think is most crucial to the success of these process requirements?

Ask the participants for an explanation of their ideas. Using probing questions, such as: ‘Can you explain...’, ‘What makes that important to you...’, ‘Tell me more...’

Collect the input of the participants on yellow sticky notes that you write yourself. Place the sticky notes on the prepared flip chart 2 as shown in Figure AIV.2. Use a few keywords to paraphrase the participants’ words. Ask for confirmation when in doubt.

Figure AIV.2. Prepared flip chart 2.

Finish Exercise 1 with a discussion of the working definition in general. Are there aspects outside the four clusters of process requirements that the participants feel are missing? What is the relative importance of the four clusters of requirements?

EXERCISE 2. EXPERIENCES OF PARTICIPANTS

Timeframe: 20 minutes

- Pair-share: 5 minutes
- Group share: 15 minutes

Objectives

- To exchange practical experiences with RRI processes among participants;
- To enhance the experienced connection to the RRI movement.

This exercise is intended to tap into the personal experience of the participants with processes that involved one or more of the four clusters of process requirements and outcomes. The exercise consists of two steps and makes use of the pair-share principle. First, the participants discuss their experiences in pairs; then they share the commonalities and differences with the rest of the group.

- We have just talked about the RRI process and the requirements that are needed to come to acceptable outcomes. I now want to ask you to discuss your own experience with respect to working with this kind of outcomes and requirements, together with your neighbour. Use **5 minutes**.

After 5 minutes:

- Thank you. I now would like you to share the most prominent experiences with the rest of the group. Let's start with you.

Collect the input of the participants on pink post-its that you write yourself. Use a few keywords to paraphrase the participants' words. Ask for confirmation when in doubt. Put the pink post-its next to the yellow post-it on flip chart 2. Use 15 minutes to discuss the experiences.

BREAK (suggested time for a coffee break; adapt time to your local needs)

Session 3: Compilation of promising RRI practices

EXERCISE 3. STRONG AND WEAK POINTS OF PROMISING PRACTICES

Timeframe: 50 minutes

- Explanation: 5 minutes
- Part B (individual): 10 minutes
- Pair-share: 10 minutes
- Part B (pairs): 5 minutes
- Four-group discussion: 20 minutes

Objectives

- To obtain an understanding of strong/weak points of the provided promising practices from the perspective of the participants.

Show the next slide of the Powerpoint presentation to make the step from the “why” and “what” of RRI to the “how” of RRI in practice. Explain the participants briefly (5 minutes) about promising RRI practices, reviewing these aspects:

- Promising practices
 - can be concrete instruments, activities, programs or organisations that provide a successful strategy for one or more of the process requirements of RRI;
 - are innovative and feasible approaches beyond the common practice;
 - strive towards the RRI outcomes;
 - have considerable and assessable positive effects;
 - are transferable to other organizations, initiatives or contexts.

Distribute the question sheet part B to every participant.

- As preparation to this workshop we asked you to think of a promising practice of RRI and fill in a question sheet. Now we would like you to fill in the second part (part B) of the sheet keeping in mind the previous session about the working definition. You have **10 minutes**.

Make sure to bring extra copies of part A of the question sheet. It could be that a participant did not fill in the sheet. Ask this person to fill in both part A and part B at this moment.

After 10 minutes:

- Thank you. Please turn to your neighbour and briefly explain to each other the promising practices you brought. Discuss why they are promising practices and what are the strong and weak points of the practices. List the strong and weak points you consider most interesting on separate post-its. Use green Post-its for the strong points and pink Post-its for the weak points. You have another **10 minutes**.

After 10 minutes:

- Take **5 minutes** to complete part B of the question sheet with new strong and weak points that have come up in the conversation.

After 5 minutes:

- Thank you. For the next exercise join another couple to make a group of four. Discuss the strong and weak points you identified. Try to be as specific as possible. Explain to each other what exactly makes this strong/weak point RRI (or not). Cluster the different post-its on a blank flip chart and provide the clusters with a title. You will have **20 minutes**.

EXERCISE 4. WHAT CHARACTERIZES PROMISING PRACTICES?

Timeframe: 25 minutes

Objectives

- To obtain an understanding of the characteristics of a promising RRI practice from the perspective of the participants.

Return to the plenary session. Collect the results of the small group discussions together with the whole group of participants:

- Let's come together again. Share your cluster titles with us and please explain your ideas. What points were most important or interesting?

Develop the discussion of strong and weak points of promising practices together with the participants. Make sure the cluster titles are written down on a flip chart in front of the group by you or your assistant.

- To finish this session on promising practices I want to ask you some questions about this discussion: What do you notice, what stands out? What was most often discussed or most important? Which of the strong points were often mentioned? What did you expect would come up in this discussion, but did not?

Afterwards, please collect the question sheets, both part A and part B.

WRAP-UP

Timeframe: 5 minutes

Take **5 minutes** to close down Sessions 2 and 3 and offer space for additional comments, ideas, questions and suggestions. Invite the participants to lunch. After lunch, an energizer may be done to enhance energy levels and to create a friendly and open atmosphere.

LUNCH BREAK (suggested time for the lunch break; adapt time to your local needs)

Session 4: Stakeholder consultation

EXERCISE 5. INTRODUCTION TO SESSION 4

Timeframe: 20 minutes (or less if there are no newcomers)

- Explanation: 20 minutes (or less)

Objectives

- Ensure participants understand the objectives of Session 4.
- Allow participants to get to know each other (only in case of new participants).

If new persons come only for Session 4, a short RRI Tools project introduction and a short summary of Sessions 2 and 3 should be given separately to the newcomers before starting Session 4.

At the beginning of Session 4 new participants should also be introduced to the rest of the group (if not done before), as well as let them know about the empty flip chart (Session 2, Exercise 0).

Moderator then introduces Session 4 objectives and expected outcomes.

- After our discussions in the previous sessions we would like to dedicate this session to look at specific needs of the stakeholders in terms of RRI. Based on your daily work experiences we will discuss and collect the most relevant aspects and requirements, from your different perspectives, that are necessary to implement the RRI concept, and will come up with some suggestions on how to achieve these requirements.
- We will start with the following exercise to identify opportunities and obstacles in relation to the RRI concept.

EXERCISE 6. OBSTACLES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Timeframe: 45minutes

- Pair-share: 20 minutes
- Plenary share: 25 minutes

Objectives

- Participants think about opportunities and obstacles related to working more closely with the RRI process and collect them.

In this exercise we mix pairs of different stakeholder groups. The aim is to exchange experiences and produce opportunity and obstacle cards with the different stakeholder perspectives.

The exercise consists of two steps:

Firstly the participants, grouped in pairs, identify opportunities and obstacles related to their daily work and exchange about them, writing these aspects on coloured cards (one colour for obstacles, one colour for opportunities). Secondly a list of two columns is created in a plenary exercise.

Note: It is not necessary that both stakeholders of the pair agree on each aspect, each of them has just to put her/his initials on those aspects relevant for her/his stakeholder group. *Example: Pair composed by 1 Researcher and 1 Educator. If an aspect is relevant for both of them they put the initials of both groups: RES, EDU; if it is only relevant for, e.g., the educator, they just put EDU.*

If not done before (see Session 1), introduce the abbreviation code scheme as follows:

Stakeholder group	Initials
Civil Society Organisations	CSO
Education Community	EDU
Industry and Business	IND
Policymakers	POL
Researchers and Innovators	RES

Ask participants to sit together in pairs (one group of three is possible). This activity could also be carried out as 'paired walks' (especially recommended after lunch).

- Please sit together in pairs with colleagues of a different stakeholder group than yours. Think about obstacles and opportunities in your work related to the RRI concept (what is hindering, what could be supporting) and write as many obstacles and opportunities as you want on cards of different colours. Please put on each card your stakeholder group initials (e.g., POL for policymakers, RES for researchers, etc.) only if the aspect is relevant for your group.
- Please write only one aspect per card. You can write as many cards as you want. Only use flip chart markers. You have **20 minutes**.

Call the pairs back into the plenary.

Guide the clustering on a prepared pin wall with two columns.

Ask one pair of participants to present their cards to the group briefly and give further explanations, if necessary.

Pin the cards in the appropriate column. Start with the obstacles and end with the opportunities.

- May I have one of the obstacle cards? Thank you. Could you please explain what you have written down?

Ask the participants for an explanation of their idea using probing questions, such as: 'Can you explain...', 'What makes that important to you...', 'Tell me more...'

While collecting the cards cluster them directly on the board (in the two columns, starting with obstacles and then moving to opportunities). Group together related aspects asking participants for help/clarification/agreement to keep them focused. Use a different colour card to create a title of each

cluster.

Ask pairs to join in and relate to the already pinned cards, one pair after the other, using the pop-corn method (see section E.4.2, Exercise 6).

- Does anybody else have the same point?

Check if this is indeed the same. Then ask:

- Does someone have a totally different point?

Etc., etc. till all pairs have added their cards and table is complete.

Repetitions and overlaps become visible this way and also if some aspects were mentioned by different stakeholders or just once.

The plenary can finally see the whole picture. Give a short wrap-up identifying the clustered topics.

BREAK (suggested time for a coffee break; adapt time to your local needs)

EXERCISE 7. IDENTIFY ACTIONS AND SOLUTIONS

Timeframe: 35 minutes

- Group work: 35 minutes

Objectives

- Work out lists of suggested actions/solutions per stakeholder group based on the formulated obstacles and opportunities.

Participants come together in homogeneous stakeholder groups. They discuss from the perspective of their groups the list of obstacles and opportunities as put together in Exercise 6. To start with, they decide which of the identified clustered topics are the most relevant for them. Along these topics they discuss and formulate actions and/or solutions that reflect their needs. Encourage participants to pick more than one topic.

Exercises 7 and 8 are the core elements of Session 4, which should provide a deeper understanding of the needs of the different stakeholder groups. The important and difficult task is to come up with needs and requirements based on the formulated opportunities and obstacles. Therefore, in Exercise 7 participants are asked to formulate suggested actions/solutions for the identified topics. They have to be briefed carefully on how to transform aspects into these actions/solutions. General and open formulated solutions, such as “more money”, should be avoided. Actions/solutions should be formulated as concrete, grounded and practical as possible. Participants discuss in homogeneous stakeholder groups and prepare to present the outcomes in Exercise 8.

In case the groups move to different rooms, make sure they all have the list of opportunities and obstacles to work with. For instance, during the previous break you can take pictures of the clusters with tablets and provide them to the groups; or copy the clusters on new flip charts and give them to the groups.

- Please split into 5 groups according to your stakeholder affiliation (*give further instructions according to your premises*). Take flip charts and markers with you. Write your stakeholder group affiliation on your flip chart. Choose the most relevant aspect among the clustered obstacles and opportunities for your stakeholder group and come back with a list of formulated actions and/or solutions for this aspect. If you have enough time, choose more aspects. Formulate actions and solutions as precisely as possible. Actions/solutions should be formulated as concrete, grounded and practical as possible (*give examples of general, not-acceptable solutions, such as “more money”*). Take **35 minutes**.

EXERCISE 8. COMPILATION OF NEEDS FOR STAKEHOLDER ACTIONS AND SOLUTIONS

Timeframe: 60 minutes

- Groups presentations: 25 minutes
- Plenary brainstorm: 35 minutes

Objectives

- To think about what stakeholders need in order to achieve the formulated actions/solutions. To produce a list of needs per stakeholder groups.

The stakeholder groups come back to the plenary and present their lists of actions and solutions in 25 minutes (5 minutes per group). The flip charts are pinned on a pin wall. After the presentation of the 5 groups, the plenary brainstorms on what is needed to make these actions and solutions work. The moderator guides the brainstorm and integrates the existing flip charts with new inputs coming from the plenary. If needed, use a new empty flip chart to write new needs as they arise from the plenary. Also, the moderator can use coloured cards to add the stakeholder group affiliation to the actions/solutions as they are discussed in the plenary. The aim is, at the end of the exercise, to come up with revised and finalised flip charts per stakeholder groups' needs (including suggestions for precise actions and needed tools).

- You have gathered the lists of requirements based on the opportunities and obstacles formulated in the previous exercise. I now want each group to present very briefly their list. Which group would like to start?

After all the group presentations (25 minutes):

- You have heard all presentations now, take a look at the list and let's think about what precisely is needed to make these solutions work?
- Some of these aspects might be tasks or tools for other stakeholder groups than yours. We might have to shift or duplicate some of the items. All together we will try to create one final revised list per stakeholder group.

You have **35 minutes** to collect inputs from the plenary and work out the final lists of stakeholders' needs.

In case the brainstorm is not as effective as it should be and participants have difficulties in brainstorming on their needs and tools, you can allow them to reflect for 10 or 15 minutes in their stakeholder group. Afterwards, ask the groups to present their needs and brainstorm in plenary again. This variation to the exercise should be adopted only if the brainstorm does not have enough outcomes (lack of ideas/needs/tools, participants do not interact, etc.).

Once the brainstorm is over thank the participants and move to the wrap-up and closing of the workshop.

Closure, feedback, and interpersonal exchange

Timeframe: 20 minutes

- Session 4 and Exercise 0 wrap-up: 5 minutes
- Results and CoP info: 2 minutes
- Evaluation questionnaire: 5 minutes
- Feedback round: 5-10 minutes
- Follow up survey and closure: 1-2 minutes

Objectives

- To summarize the main results from Session 4.
- To tackle open issues (Exercise 0) not considered during the whole workshop.
- To inform on workshop results analysis.
- To invite joining the Community of Practice.
- To fill evaluation questionnaire (Annex V).
- To provide feedback round.
- To announce follow up e-mail survey (Annex VI) and close workshop.

Moderator closes and wraps up results of Session 4, also taking into consideration the open issues not tackled during the whole workshop but collected on flip chart (Exercise 0).

Moderator thanks the participants and explains what will happen with the workshop outcomes: the global analysis of the results from all the hubs will give us an overview of the differences across stakeholder groups and European countries and will allow us to develop the RRI Toolkit tailoring the tools to the needs expressed by each group. The workshop is also the starting point for building a Community of Practice across Europe and for future collaborations between the participants and the project.

Moving to the Consultation Workshop closure, the moderator will distribute the evaluation questionnaire for feedback (Annex V) and give a few minutes to fill it.

Then the moderator will freely adapt the most appropriate feedback round to give participants the chance to tell what they liked or did not like from the whole event (Sessions 1 to 4), what they take back home from the activity, if the knowledge/content/contacts will be useful for them in the future, and

suggestions for improvement. It is suggested that you do not make a tour de table, since participants tend to disconnect. Instead, make use of the pop-corn method in combination with one of these examples for feedback rounds:

- “Eye-opener”: ask participants to distil one major impacting idea from the event;
- 3 word feedback: ask participants to summarize the workshop day in 3 words;
- Sandwich feedback: ask participants to say 1 negative aspect of the workshop day that is “sandwiched” between 2 positive aspects/lessons learnt.

Moderator finally announces a **follow up short e-mail survey** (Annex VI) to be sent immediately after the Consultation Workshop and closes the event.

In sum, in the closing session you:

- Wrap up Session 4.
- Tackle open issues (Exercise 0).
- Explain outcomes analysis.
- Invite to join the CoP.
- Distribute evaluation questionnaire (Annex V).
- Do a Consultation Workshop feedback round.
- Announce follow up e-mail survey.
- Thank participants and close the event.

Summary table

Exercise	Objectives	Instructions for moderator	Materials needed <i>(check Annex VIII for clarifications)</i>	Time (')
Preparation	To prepare the workshop in time and to ensure the workshop starts on time.	Be on time to prepare the room: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Table and chair setting · Name tags (colour-coded and make one for you and your assistant(s)) · Documentation for you and your assistant(s) · Stationery materials for you and your assistant(s) · Audio-recorder · Projector · Screen · Laptop/PC · PowerPoint presentation · Flip charts · Documentation for participants · Stationery materials for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 18-20 chairs · Tables for 18-20 people · 18-20 coloured name tags <i>(if not coloured, add 20 small coloured sticky dots in 5 different colours)</i> · 2 checklist hardcopies · List of participants contact details <i>(if not completed yet)</i> · Participants list for signature · 40 informed consent copies · 1 Manual hardcopy · 2 scripts hardcopies in your own language · 2 hardcopies of this table in your own language · Workshop reporting template 	Before start

		<p>participants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Dissemination materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 1 audio recorder (prefer. digital) · 1 projector · 1 screen · 1 laptop/PC linked to projector · PowerPoint workshop presentation · 3 flip charts · 15 blank flip charts · 2 prepared flip charts: stakeholders and process requirements · 20 black markers · 15 markers (other colours) · 20 pens · 1 tape roll for sticking flip charts and other papers to the wall · 2 pin walls -one prepared for two columns- (if not available, use flip charts taped to wall) · 100 pins · 300 moderation cards of 3 colours (100 each colour) · 3 stacks of sticky notes (3 colours – yellow, pink, green –, 7.5x7.5 cm size) 	
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 20 copies of the workshop agenda · 5 extra copies (blank) of the promising RRI practice question sheet (part A) · 20 copies of the promising RRI practice question sheet (part B) · 20 hardcopies of the evaluation questionnaire · A4 spare paper · 1 RRI Tools roll-up · 2 RRI Tools A3 posters · 50-100 RRI Tools leaflets 	
Session 1				
Welcome and introduction	<p>To give practical information and to register participants.</p> <p>To introduce the project, the workshop and your role.</p> <p>To allow participants to get to know each other and create a climate of open exchange.</p>	<p>Make sure all participants sign list and informed consent.</p> <p>Let participants define themselves according to one (or more) stakeholder groups.</p> <p>Keep introductory round short.</p> <p>Set house rules</p> <p>Make sure participants understand</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 18-20 coloured name tags (<i>if not coloured, add 20 small coloured sticky dots in 5 different colours</i>) · 1 marker · PowerPoint presentation 	<p>35'</p> <p>Intro: 20'</p> <p>Project: 10'</p> <p>Workshop: 5'</p>

		the structure and objectives of the workshop and how does it fit in the project.		
Session 2				
Exercise 0. On-going activity	To introduce the empty flip chart.	Remark that there you will collect any questions/issues not tackled during the exercises to be answered later or included in the workshop report.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 1 empty flip chart · 1 marker 	1'
Exercise 1. The RRI working definition	<p>To introduce and discuss the working definition with the participants.</p> <p>To receive feedback on the working definition.</p>	<p>a) Use the PowerPoint presentation to explain what RRI is and how we define it.</p> <p>b) Facilitate discussions about the why, the who and the when of RRI by writing down interesting notions on a blank flip chart and by asking in-depth questions, if needed.</p> <p>c) Ask participants to think of the most crucial aspects to the success of the process requirements. Collect their ideas by writing them down on</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PowerPoint presentation · 2 prepared flip charts: stakeholders and process requirements · Yellow sticky notes · Markers 	<p>75'</p> <p>a: 20'</p> <p>b: 25'</p> <p>c+d: 30'</p>

		<p>yellow sticky notes and place them on the flip chart with the four clusters of process requirements.</p> <p>d) Finish Exercise 1 with a discussion about the working definition in general.</p>		
<p>Exercise 2. Experiences of participants</p>	<p>To exchange practical experiences with RRI processes among participants.</p> <p>To enhance the experienced connection to the RRI movement.</p>	<p>a) Let participants discuss their experiences with processes that involved one or more of the four clusters of process requirements and outcomes in pairs.</p> <p>b) Ask them to share the commonalities and differences with the group. Collect the participants' input on pink sticky notes you write yourself. Put these notes next to the yellow ones on the flip chart of process requirements (Ex. 1).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PowerPoint presentation · Flip chart of process requirements from Exercise 1 · Pink sticky notes · Markers 	<p>20'</p> <p>a: 5'</p> <p>b: 15'</p>
<p>BREAK</p>				<p>Adapt to local needs</p>

Session 3				
Exercise 3. Strong and weak points of promising practices	To obtain an understanding of strong and weak points of the provided promising practices from the perspective of the participants.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Explain participants about promising RRI practices. b) Distribute the question sheet (part B) to every participant and ask them to fill it in individually. <i>(If someone forgot to fill in or to bring part A, give them the opportunity to fill it in now.)</i> c) Have them discuss their promising practices in light of RRI with their neighbour. Ask them to list the strong and weak points on separate sticky notes (green for strong, pink for weak). d) Give them a few moments to complete the question sheet (part B) in pairs. e) Let pairs team up with another pairs and have them cluster the strong and weak points. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PowerPoint presentation · 4 blank flip charts · Green and pink sticky notes · Markers · 20 question sheets (part B) · 5 extra question sheets (part A) 	50' a) 5' b) 10' c) 10' d) 5' e) 20'

Exercise 4. What characterizes promising RRI practices?	To obtain an understanding of the characteristics of a promising RRI practice from the perspective of the participants.	<p>a) Ask participants to come together again. Have them explain the most often mentioned or most thought-provoking strong and weak points of promising RRI practices and visualize the discussion on a blank flip chart.</p> <p>b) Ask participants questions referring to what they think characterizes a (promising) practice of RRI.</p> <p>Collect all question sheets (parts A and B).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · PowerPoint presentation · Blank flip chart · Flip charts from Exercise 3 · Markers 	25'
Wrap-up	To close down Sessions 2&3.	<p>Offer space for additional comments, ideas, questions and suggestions.</p> <p>Invite participants to lunch.</p>		5'
LUNCH Suggestion: <i>energize</i> your participants after lunch				45-60' Adapt to local needs

Session 4				
<p>Exercise 5. Introduction to Session 4</p>	<p><i>To allow participants to get to know each other (only if newcomers).</i></p> <p>To ensure participants understand the objectives of Session 4</p> <p>To revive a friendly atmosphere.</p>	<p><i>Only if new persons attend! Ask newcomers to sign list and informed consent. Give them a separate introduction to the project, the workshop and a summary of what has been done in Sessions 2 and 3. Then introduce newcomers to the rest of the group.</i></p> <p>Introduce Session 4.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Tables and chairs in a circle <p><i>Only if there are newcomers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Coloured name tags (if not coloured, add 20 small coloured sticky dots in 5 different colours) · PowerPoint presentation 	<p>20' or less</p>
<p>Exercise 6. Obstacles and opportunities</p>	<p>To think about opportunities and obstacles related to the RRI concept from the different stakeholder perspectives.</p>	<p>a) Participants sit together in pairs (one group of three) and write cards.</p> <p>b) Ask participants to present their cards to the group briefly and give further explanations.</p> <p>While collecting the cards cluster them directly on the board (in the 2 columns, starting with obstacles and then moving to opportunities), put overlaps together. If necessary, add titles to the clusters (use cards</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Moderation cards of three colours · Markers (do NOT use pens!) · Pinwall prepared for two columns · 100 pins <p>Display codes:</p> <p>CSO: civil society organisations</p> <p>EDU: education community</p>	<p>45'</p> <p>a) 20'</p> <p>b) 25'</p>

		<p>of different colour).</p> <p>Give short wrap-up after completion of table and identify clustered topics.</p>	<p>IND: industry and business</p> <p>POL: policymakers</p> <p>RES: researchers</p>	
BREAK				Adapt to local needs
Exercise 7. Identify actions and solutions	<p>To identify suggested actions/solutions per stakeholder group based on the formulated obstacles and opportunities</p>	<p>Ask participants to come together in homogeneous stakeholder groups (5 groups with at least 3 persons each).</p> <p>Ask participants to formulate suggested actions/solutions for the identified topics.</p> <p>Brief them on how to transform aspects into these actions/solutions. General and open formulated solutions, such as “more money”, have to be avoided. Actions and solutions should be formulated as concrete, grounded and practical as possible.</p> <p><i>E.g., obstacle: no political</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Pinwall from Exercise 6 · 5 flip charts (1 per group) · 5 markers (1 per group) 	35'

		<i>awareness. Solutions: policy briefs. Small guiding brochures on basic understanding and requirements of the RRI concept.</i>		
Exercise 8. Compilation of needs for stakeholder actions and solutions	<p>To think about what stakeholders need in order to achieve the formulated actions or solutions.</p> <p>To produce a list of needs per stakeholder group.</p>	<p>Ask stakeholder groups to come back to plenary with their lists of suggested solutions according to most relevant aspects.</p> <p>a) Shortly each group presents their list (5' per group); plenary can comment and complement.</p> <p>b) Plenary brainstorms on what is needed to make these actions and solutions work.</p> <p>Guide the brainstorm and integrate new inputs coming from the plenary into the flip charts.</p> <p>If needed, use a new empty flip chart to write new needs as they arise from the plenary.</p> <p>Use coloured cards to add the stakeholder group affiliation to the actions/solutions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Flip charts from Exercise 7 · Empty flip charts (if needed) · 1 marker · Additional coloured moderation cards 	<p>60'</p> <p>a) 25'</p> <p>b) 35'</p>

<p>Closure, feedback and interpersonal exchange</p>	<p>To summarize main results from Session 4.</p> <p>To tackle open issues (Exercise 0).</p> <p>To explain what will happen with workshop outcomes.</p> <p>To invite to join the Community of Practice.</p> <p>To fill evaluation questionnaire.</p> <p>To provide feedback round.</p> <p>To announce follow up e-mail survey.</p> <p>To close event.</p>	<p>Give a wrap up of results from Session 4, also taking into consideration the open issues not tackled during the session but collected on flip chart (Exercise 0).</p> <p>Clearly explain and emphasize how will the workshop results be analysed and used to define and tailor specific tools.</p> <p>Invite participants to register in the CoP as a starting point for further collaborations with the project.</p> <p>Distribute evaluation questionnaires and give participants time to fill them.</p> <p>Start a feedback round.</p> <p>Announce the follow up e-mail survey to be sent immediately after the Consultation Workshop.</p> <p>Thank participants and close the workshop.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Open issues flip chart (Ex. 0) · 20 copies of the evaluation questionnaire · 20 pens 	<p>20'</p>
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Annex V

Evaluation Questionnaire

Annex V. Evaluation questionnaire

NHCs will have to translate this questionnaire to their own language keeping its content without modifications to prevent local bias in the analysis of results.

7. What did you like least about this event?**Why?****8. Please circle ONE rate for each 'Before' and 'After' the event statements.**

	Not very well	Somewhat well	Moderately well	Very well
a) I understood the principles of RRI.				
a. Before the event?	1	2	3	4
b. After the event?	1	2	3	4
 b) I know how to implement RRI aspects in my daily working environment.				
a. Before the event?	1	2	3	4
b. After the event?	1	2	3	4
 c) I am aware of the needs, possible solutions and necessary tools of my stakeholder group for implementing RRI.				
a. Before the event?	1	2	3	4
b. After the event?	1	2	3	4

9. Do you plan to use the information from this workshop?
 Yes No

If yes, how?**My general comments and suggestions for improving this workshop are:**

Thank you for your time!
Please return this questionnaire to the organiser!

Annex VI

Follow up email survey template

Annex VI. Follow up e-mail survey template

The following questions will be sent via e-mail right after the Consultation Workshop both to participants in the event and to those candidates who could not finally attend the workshop (see Section F). NHCs should translate these questions into their own local language.

a) E-mail text to be sent to all workshop participants.

Dear Mrs./Mr. *[surname of participant]*,

Thank you for participating in our RRI Tools Stakeholder Consultation workshop/meeting on [date] in [location]. As announced during the workshop, we would like to give you an opportunity to complement the results of the event. These outcomes will be considered in the analysis of the workshop as well.

Please just reply to this e-mail and insert your answers directly in the text below. Please send this mail no later than *[date, approximately 10 days later]*.

We will keep you updated on the results of the project consultations across Europe and will approach you again for further project activities, looking forward for a fruitful collaboration. You could also start being part of our Community of Practice by registering [here](#).

Thank you in advance.

Best regards,

[Name Surname]

- 1) Which aspects do you consider as the main obstacles and opportunities in the RRI concept from your (stakeholder) point of view?

- 2) What solutions do you think could address these issues best?

- 3) Do you have any tools in mind that could support the acquired solutions? Are there any existing ones? Which new tools could complement the existing ones?

- 4) Do you have any additional comments to the working definition of RRI as presented during the workshop?

- 5) Can you think of more promising practices of RRI that would be interesting for the RRI Tools project?

b) E-mail text to be sent to contacts who did not attend the workshop.

In this case attach to the e-mail the RRI information sheet, the examples of promising RRI practices, and the promising RRI practice question sheet (part A), all found in Annex III.

Dear Mrs./Mr. *[surname of participant]*,

As recently announced, the first RRI Tools Stakeholder Consultation workshop/meeting has taken place on *[date]* in *[location]*. In order to allow for a wider involvement of stakeholders, we would like to give you an opportunity to complement the results of the workshop by contributing to what was discussed at the event. These outcomes will be considered in the analysis of the workshop as well.

Please just reply to this e-mail and insert your answers directly in the text below. Please send this mail no later than *[date, approximately 10 days later]*.

We will keep you updated on the results of the project consultations across Europe and will approach you again for further project activities, looking forward for a fruitful collaboration. You could also start being part of our Community of Practice by registering [here](#).

Thank you in advance.

Best regards,

[Name Surname]

1) Which aspects do you consider as the main obstacles and opportunities in the RRI concept from your (stakeholder) point of view?

2) What solutions do you think could address these issues best?

3) Do you have any tools in mind that could support the acquired solutions? Are there any existing ones? Which new tools could complement the existing ones?

4) Do you have any additional comments to the working definition of RRI as presented during the workshop?

5) Can you think of more promising practices of RRI that would be interesting for the RRI Tools project?

Annex VII

Reporting Template

Annex VII. Reporting template

General information

City, country:

Date, time:

Organiser (national hub coordinator):

Moderator:

Assistant(s):

Observer(s):

Participants information

In the second column to the right, please indicate the type of organisation according to the stakeholder mapping tables (Annex I) for the most relevant stakeholder group represented by the participant.

Person	Age	Gender	Stakeholder group	Expertise	Region/locality	Type of organisation	Present in session(s)
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							
12							
13							
14							
15							

Recruitment information

Was it particularly hard to recruit participants from a particular stakeholder group? Please tell us more about the recruitment process and any problems you faced.

Session 2: RRI working definition

<p>Exercise 1</p> <p>The RRI working definition</p>	<p>Provide a small summary of the discussion about the why of RRI:</p> <p>Provide a small summary of the discussion about the who and when of RRI:</p> <p>Provide a small summary of the discussion concerning what is thought to be most crucial to the success of the process requirements:</p> <p>Add photos of the visualizations:</p> <p>Summarize (or translate) information below:</p> <p>Provide a small summary of the discussion about the working definition in general (address the most relevant aspects of the definition; aspects outside the four clusters that might be missing; other important questions or remarks).</p>
<p>Exercise 2</p> <p>Experiences of participants</p>	<p>Add photos of the visualizations</p>

	<p>Summarize (or translate) information below:</p> <p>Provide a small summary of the discussion (elaborate on keywords from post-its)</p>
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Session 3: Compilation of promising RRI practices

<p>Exercise 3 Strong and weak points of promising practices</p>	<p>Add photos of the visualizations and provide translations of clusters made by participants.</p>
<p>Exercise 4 What characterizes promising RRI practices?</p>	<p>Add photos of the visualization and provide translations of the clusters developed during the discussion</p> <p>Provide a small summary of the discussion (elaborate on keywords from post-its)</p>
<p>Wrap-up</p>	<p>Summarize the most important questions or remarks that have been made at the end of Sessions 2 and 3.</p>

Session 4: Stakeholder Consultation

1. Activities observation

<p>Exercise 6</p> <p>Obstacles and opportunities</p>	<p>Table of Obstacles/Opportunities with stakeholder initials on cards.</p> <p><i>Type all aspects per column (add rows as needed). Type cluster titles, if any. Please explain any cultural/local references, if any.</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="469 533 1422 1137"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="469 533 730 685">Obstacles</th> <th data-bbox="730 533 904 685"></th> <th data-bbox="904 533 1251 685">Opportunities</th> <th data-bbox="1251 533 1422 685"></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="469 685 730 837"></td> <td data-bbox="730 685 904 837" style="text-align: center;"><i>Stakeholder group</i></td> <td data-bbox="904 685 1251 837"></td> <td data-bbox="1251 685 1422 837" style="text-align: center;"><i>Stakeholder group</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="469 837 730 990"></td> <td data-bbox="730 837 904 990"></td> <td data-bbox="904 837 1251 990"></td> <td data-bbox="1251 837 1422 990"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="469 990 730 1137"></td> <td data-bbox="730 990 904 1137"></td> <td data-bbox="904 990 1251 1137"></td> <td data-bbox="1251 990 1422 1137"></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Note comments and questions discussed or raised within the group:</p>	Obstacles		Opportunities			<i>Stakeholder group</i>		<i>Stakeholder group</i>								
Obstacles		Opportunities															
	<i>Stakeholder group</i>		<i>Stakeholder group</i>														
<p>Exercise 7</p> <p>Identify actions and solutions – Group work</p>	<p>Suggested actions/solution lists per stakeholder group.</p> <p><i>(Type lists as stated on flip chart – add bullets as needed. Type the name of the obstacle/opportunity being addressed)</i></p> <p><i>Civil Society Organisations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - - - 																

	<p><i>Education Community</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - - - <p><i>Industry and Business</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - - - <p><i>Policymakers</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - - - <p><i>Researchers</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - - -
<p>Exercise 8</p> <p>Compilation of needs – Brainstorming</p>	<p>Brainstorming list of needs per stakeholder group.</p> <p><i>(Type final lists as worked out by the plenary – add bullet points as needed)</i></p> <p><i>Civil Society Organisations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - - - -

	<p><i>Education Community</i></p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p><i>Industry and Business</i></p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p><i>Policymakers</i></p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p><i>Researchers</i></p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>-</p> <p>Notes on comments:</p>
<p>Feedback round</p>	<p>Notes on comments:</p>

Not tackled aspects, open questions/issues	Type list as stated on flip chart – add bullets as needed. - - - -
Additional	Comments, issues, topics raised during the workshop (not documented on flip charts). <i>Four or five main points, plus any points that really surprised you, any important comments that should be taken into account by UCL during their analysis, etc.. It is important to communicate the general feeling; for instance, did you notice any particular group dynamic? Did any participants dominate the discussions? Did you have any problem in moderating the workshop or any specific exercise? Do you think participants were engaged/interested/positive about the workshop?</i>

2. General Reflection and Documentation

Self-assessment by organisers on workshop methodologies, take up by participants, atmosphere, hindering and supporting aspects, etc.

	<i>Explanations</i>
Pros	
Cons	

Annex VIII

Checklist for organising the workshop

Annex VIII. Checklist for organising the workshop

1. BEFORE the event – Aims, objectives of the workshop, host team and invitations

- Make yourself clear with the objectives of the workshop. Read the Manual carefully.
- Determine a person that will act as **moderator** (person who took part in the training in Copenhagen) and a person that will act as **assistant** (who will help the moderation as well as the participants).
- Brief the assistant on the workshop content and specific tasks (supports the moderator throughout the workshop in assisting participants, distributing required materials, leading groups to other rooms, conducting the exercises, taking notes and pictures, taking care of the documentation for reporting and attendance, filling the reporting/observation template).
- Inform EuroScience of the date of the event no later than 6 weeks in advance, so that communication can be planned accordingly.
- Select and invite workshop participants accordingly to the instructions in sections B.1-B.4 at least 6-8 weeks before the event. Use the invitation letter provided in Annex II.
- Communicate clearly why the participation in the workshop will be of interest for the stakeholder (see B.1-B.2).
- A short summary of the project should be provided, as well as basic dissemination material, such as the leaflet - ideally translated (see B.3 and C.1).
- Make follow-up calls (if needed) 10 days after the invitation was sent to increase the response rate.
- Keep a list of all the people you invite with all relevant contact details.
- As soon as potential candidates confirm their attendance, send the information package (see B.4 for instructions and Annex III for templates). This package should also contain the practicalities, including the workshop agenda, meeting place address and how to get there - include parking options-, hotel address, contact phone numbers, tourist map of town, etc. (see B.4).
- Prepare one month before the workshop the promotional material of your institution and of RRI Tools (roll-ups, leaflets, A3 posters...) that will be displayed in the workshop, adapting them to your local language and printing the RRI Tools materials.
- Send press release to journalists 15 days before the workshop.
- Phone back journalists a few days afterwards to get feedback and know if they will tackle your activity.
- Publish posts on social media announcing your workshop, using @RRITools on Twitter to ease the retweets. Ask your networks to disseminate the information on their communication channels as well.
- Post updates about your workshop on your website and integrate the information in your newsletter.
- One week before the workshop send to participants a reminder to send you back the Promising RRI practice question sheet (part A) filled in.

2. BEFORE the event – Practical organisation

Logistics

- Hotel(s) booked
- Meeting place booked
- Lunch organised
- Breaks organised
- Beverages during the meeting organised
- Internet connection organised, including password (optional)
- Internet connection checked (optional)
- Sufficient power sockets organised
- Approximated costs calculated
- RRI Tools banner organized

Be on time! You will need time to arrange the room. This should be done before the participants can come in.

Necessary material organized and functionality checked

- Checklist (this Annex VIII) (2 copies for the moderator and the assistant)
- Tables for 18-20 people
- 18-20 chairs
- 1 RRI Tools roll-up
- 2 RRI Tools A3 posters
- 50-100 RRI Tools leaflets
- 1 screen
- 1 projector/beamer
- 1 laptop/PC linked to projector
- PowerPoint presentation of the whole workshop
- 1 audio recorder (preferably digital)
- List for participants to fill in their name and e-mail (if not in your possession)
- Participation list for signature
- Informed consent (Annex III) for signature (40 copies)
- Evaluation questionnaire (Annex V) (20 copies)
- Reporting template (Annex VII) printed for the assistant (or provided on a laptop for immediate completion)
- 18-20 name tags (folded A4/name labels or badges of 5 different colours; alternatively you can use coloured sticky dots to stick on the name tags/badges)
- 20 small coloured sticky dots in 5 different colours (only if name tags are not already coloured according to the stakeholder group affiliation!)
- Agenda of the workshop (20 copies)
- Manual (this document) (1 copy)

- Scripts of the 4 sessions (Annex IV, including Summary table) in your own language (2 copies for the moderator and the assistant)
- 5 extra copies (blank) of part A of the Promising RRI practice question sheet
- 20 copies of part B of the Promising RRI practice question sheet
- 3 flip charts (one for unsolved questions -Exercise 0- during all the workshop)
- Flip chart paper (min. 20 sheets)
- 2 prepared flip chart sheets for Exercise 1 (Annex IV, Session 2): one with the table of stakeholders (Fig. AIV.1), one with the process requirements (Fig. AIV.2)
- 1 tape roll for sticking flip charts and other papers on wall
- 2 pin walls -one prepared for two columns- (if not available, use flip charts taped to wall)
- 100 pins (not needed if pin walls not available)
- 20 black flip chart markers
- 15 flip chart markers (other colours)
- 20 pens
- 300 moderation cards of 3 colours (100 each colour; approx. 9x20 cm size)
- 3 stacks of sticky notes (3 different colours -yellow, pink, green-, at least 150 per colour; 7.5x7.5 cm size)
- A4 spare paper

Preparation of the room

- Dissemination materials
 - 1 RRI Tools roll-up highly visible
 - 2 RRI Tools A3 posters displayed on the wall
 - 50-100 RRI Tools leaflets displayed on a table
- Projector
 - turned on
 - connected to a computer
 - Slide 1 of Powerpoint workshop presentation on
- Flip charts
 - 2 on the wall
 - 1 for unsolved questions/further aspects (Exercise 0) apart from the other two
- Moderator and assistant name tags clearly written at the places where they will sit
- Tables arranged so that
 - the moderator and assistant can
 - ◆ see everybody
 - ◆ reach everybody easily when walking around
 - participants can see with relative ease
 - ◆ the PowerPoint presentation
 - ◆ the 3 flip charts on the wall

- For each participant, on their own table:
 - Name tags prepared (they will be colour coded by stakeholder group as defined by the stakeholders themselves)
 - 1 agenda (printed)
 - 1 black marker
 - 1 pen
 - 1 A4 spare sheet
 - 10 cards of 2 colours (5 each colour)
 - 10 yellow sticky notes
 - 10 pink sticky notes
 - 10 green sticky notes

3. DURING the event – Consultation Workshop

Presence and arrivals

- When people enter the room
 - Welcome them
 - Tell them where they can put their coat and luggage
 - Offer them something to drink
 - Try to establish a friendly and open environment
 - Ask them to
 - ◆ sign list of participants
 - ◆ read and sign informed consent
 - ◆ find a place to sit
 - ◆ write their names on the name tags
 - ◆ define their stakeholder group by colouring their name tag
- Signed by all participants:
 - Informed consent (section B.4 and Annex III)
 - List of participants
- Provided to each participant:
 - Agenda (hardcopy)
 - Name tags (they should define themselves according to colour code)
 - Necessary material (paper, stickers, posters, pens – see 2.)
- Pictures taken
- Social media posts on what is happening (with images, if possible) posted
- All produced posters and material collected (or captured via pictures of a high resolution camera) and stored
- Evaluation questionnaires (Annex V) filled out and collected

4. AFTER the event – Follow-up

- Media/print press release for newspapers or internet sent
- Short, informal chronicle of the workshop for the newsletter, blog, etc. sent to EuroScience (optional)
- Follow up e-mail survey (see Section F and Annex VI):
 - Sent to:
 - ◆ workshop attendees;
 - ◆ invited guests who were not able to attend the workshop;
 - reminder for the answers sent (if necessary);
 - All answers:
 - ◆ collected;
 - ◆ uploaded to RRI Tools Dropbox account (specific hub subfolder):
<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/31okaxhxikgeutx/AAClhxslgVoia26fHeG4WTMOa>
- Reporting material (see Section G):
 - Reporting template (Annex VII);
 - Filled in Question Sheets (parts A and B, translated into English) for each promising RRI practice put forward by the participants or the NHCs;
 - Individual files for pictures (optional);
 - ◆ collected;
 - ◆ uploaded to RRI Tools Dropbox account (specific hub subfolder):
<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/31okaxhxikgeutx/AAClhxslgVoia26fHeG4WTMOa>
- Contacts follow up: invited to sign up to the newsletter and the social media to stay updated
- Messages about the outcomes of the workshop posted on the social media, newsletter and website of your institution and RRI Tools
- Press release about the outcomes of the workshop sent to journalists
- 10 promising practices selected, translated and sent to Athena (m.rijnen@vu.nl)
- NHC contacted by Athena to discuss which promising practices will be used for the Online Questionnaire (see Deliverable 1.2)

